

Democritus University of Thrace - Faculty of Engineering

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Division of Electronics and Information Systems Technology

Automatic Control Systems and Robotics Laboratory

Multiple Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Motion Planning and Routing for Optimized Remote Sensing Operations

Doctoral Dissertation of: **Savvas Apostolidis** | Academic Supervisor:
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ΔΗΜΟΚΡΙΤΕΙΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΘΡΑΚΗΣ
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Σχεδιασμός Τροχιάς και Δρομολόγηση Πολλαπλών
Μη Επανδρωμένων Εναερίων Οχημάτων για
Βελτιστοποιημένες Αποστολές Τηλεπισκόπησης

Διδακτορική Διατριβή του:
ΣΑΒΒΑ ΑΠΟΣΤΟΛΙΔΗ

Επιβλέπων:
ΚΑΘ. Η. ΚΟΣΜΑΤΟΠΟΥΛΟΣ, ΔΠΘ

Ξάνθη, Μάιος 2025

Η έγκριση της διδακτορικής διατριβής από το Τμήμα Ηλεκτρολόγων Μηχανικών και Μηχανικών Υπολογιστών της Πολυτεχνικής Σχολής του Δημοκρίτειου Πανεπιστημίου Θράκης, δεν υποδηλώνει την αποδοχή οποιασδήποτε γνώμης του συγγραφέα.

Η ΕΠΤΑΜΕΛΗΣ ΕΞΕΤΑΣΤΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ:

Ο ΕΠΒΛΕΠΩΝ:

ΚΑΘ. Η. ΚΟΣΜΑΤΟΠΟΥΛΟΣ, ΔΠΘ

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ΚΑΘ. Σ. ΧΑΤΖΗΧΡΙΣΤΟΦΗΣ, ΠΑΝ/ΜΙΟ ΝΕΑΠΟΛΙΣ ΠΑΦΟΣ

ΕΡΕΤΝΗΤΗΣ Γ, Γ. ΙΩΑΝΝΑΚΗΣ, Ε.Κ. ΑΘΗΝΑ

Πρόλογος

Το ταξίδι που ολοκληρώνεται με τη συγγραφή της παρούσας διατριβής, ξεκίνησε τον Οκτώβριο του 2018. Κατά τη διάρκεια αυτών των ετών διάφορα γεγονότα συνέβαλαν στη διαμόρφωση τόσο του αποτελέσματός της, όσο και του ίδιου του συγγραφέα της. Μια μετακόμιση, νέο εργασιακό περιβάλλον, καινούριοι συνεργάτες -κάποιοι από αυτούς πλέον φίλοι-, καινούρια πρόσωπα στη ζωή μου, αγαπημένα άτομα που έφυγαν... Μια πανδημία, καραντίνες και αυστηροί περιορισμοί κυκλοφορίας, τηλεργασία, πειράματα με drones στο πεδίο στα κρυφά και με μάσκες. Το ταξίδι δεν ήταν σύντομο, και σίγουρα ο δρόμος του είχε πολλές ανηφόρες και κατηφόρες. Φτάνοντας πλέον στον τελικό προορισμό, ή καλύτερα την τελευταία στάση πριν το επόμενο ταξίδι, αυτό που θα κρατήσω είναι οι άνθρωποι, οι στιγμές και οι εμπειρίες.

Από αυτούς, πρώτο απ' όλους θα ήθελα να ευχαριστήσω τον επιβλέποντα καθηγητή μου Ηλία Κοσματοπούλο, για την ευκαιρία που μου έδωσε να γίνω μέλος της ερευνητικής του ομάδας και να συνεργαστώ τόσο μαζί του, όσο και με τα υπόλοιπα μέλη του εργαστηρίου. Νιώθω αφάνταστα τυχερός που πραγματοποίησα τις διδακτορικές μου σπουδές υπό την επίβλεψή του, και έχοντας άμεση ή έμμεση συνεργασία με το σύνολο των ανθρώπων που επέλεξε να απαρτίζουν την ερευνητική του ομάδα. Πέρα από το ακαδημαϊκό και ερευνητικό του έργο, εκτίμησα βαθύτατα την -παρά τα όσα έχει καταφέρει- απλότητα του χαρακτήρα του, την ταπεινότητά του, και την προθυμία του να ακούσει και να βοηθήσει τον άλλον.

Ένα πολύ μεγάλο ευχαριστώ οφείλω στο μεταδιδακτορικό ερευνητή του εργαστηρίου -και πλέον φίλο- Θανάση Καπούτση, για τη συνεργασία, την καθοδήγηση, και την υποστήριξή του όλα αυτά τα χρόνια, σε ακαδημαϊκό, επαγγελματικό και προσωπικό επίπεδο. Η συμβολή του στο τελικό αποτέλεσμα της παρούσας διατριβής, και το σύνολο των δημοσιευμένων εργασιών που προέκυψαν στο πλαίσιο της, ήταν καθοριστική και κρίσιμη.

Ακόμη, ένα ξεχωριστό ευχαριστώ χρωστάω στους φίλους μου, που κατά τη διάρκεια αυτών των ετών ήταν εκεί σε όμορφες και δύσκολες στιγμές, παρέχοντας την

ανεκτίμητη υποστήριξη τους, και που ανάμεσα σε σοβαρές συζητήσεις και πλάκες χρωμάτισαν με το δικό τους μοναδικό τρόπο, και έκαναν ευχάριστα, τα χρόνια που χρειάστηκαν για την ολοκλήρωση των διδακτορικών μου σπουδών. Το ίδιο ισχύει και για το σύνολο των ανθρώπων που μπήκαν, ή έφυγαν από τη ζωή μου, αφήνοντας ο καθένας το δικό του στίγμα, και επιτελώντας το δικό τους -μικρότερο ή μεγαλύτερο- ρόλο στην ολοκλήρωση αυτού του διδακτορικού.

Φυσικά, το μεγαλύτερο ευχαριστώ πηγαίνει στην οικογένειά μου, τους γονείς μου Δημήτρη και Χρυσούλα, την αδελφή μου Γεωργία, και τους θείους μου Πρόδρομο και Έλενα. Δεν ξέρω αν θα μπορούσα να εκφράσω με λόγια -και αν ναι, σίγουρα δε θα χωρούσε σε μια μικρή παράγραφο- το πόσο και πώς ο καθένας τους με έχει στηρίξει και έχει συμβάλει στη διαμόρφωση αυτού που είμαι σήμερα. Το λιγότερο λοιπόν που θα μπορούσα να κάνω, είναι να αφιερώσω την παρούσα διατριβή σε αυτούς.

Καθώς λοιπόν αυτό το ταξίδι φτάνει στο τέλος του, ελπίζω ότι κατά τη διάρκειά του κατάφερα να συμβάλω, έστω ελάχιστα, στο ερευνητικό αντικείμενο με το οποίο καταπιάνεται η παρούσα διατριβή, και πως κομμάτια της δουλειάς που πραγματοποιήθηκε και παρουσιάζονται σε αυτό το τεύχος θα αποτελέσουν τη βάση για νέες ερευνητικές δουλειές που θα εξελίξουν περαιτέρω το επιστημονικό της πεδίο. Η ελπίδα αυτή αντανακλάται και στο σύνολο των προσβάσιμων υλοποιήσεων και δεδομένων που παρέχονται μαζί με τις δημοσιεύσεις που πραγματοποιήθηκαν κατά τη διάρκεια του. Χωρίς ακόμη να έχει σχεδιαστεί η συνέχεια του ταξιδιού, ελπίζω να εξακολουθεί να είναι δημιουργική, διατηρώντας ανθρώπους που συνάντησα κατά τη διάρκειά του στη ζωή μου, και γνωρίζοντας νέους που θα δώσουν απρόοπτες τροπές και αφορμές για νέες περιπέτειες. Μοναδική προτροπή -κυρίως στον εαυτό μου, όταν μετά από χρόνια τύχει να ξαναδιαβάσω αυτό το κείμενο- είναι ανεξαρτήτως δυσκολίας ή ταχύτητας, το ταξίδι να συνεχίζεται και οι προορισμοί του να είναι περιπετειώδεις και ενδιαφέροντες.

*Remember to look up at the stars and not down at your feet.
Try to make sense of what you see and wonder about what makes
the universe exist. Be curious. And however difficult life may seem,
there is always something you can do and succeed at. It matters that you
-don't just give up.-*

Stephen Hawking

Abstract

In the context of this dissertation we deal with the problem of motion planning and routing for multiple unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to perform effective and efficient remote sensing operations (RS). The largest part of the presented work focuses on Coverage Path Planning (CPP) and multi-agent CPP (mCPP), that is the problem of having to completely cover a designated region of interest (ROI) with one or more unmanned vehicles, while simultaneously respecting any restrictions are enforced by the ROI, vehicle(s), user(s), and operational or legal frameworks. Additionally, a gap in literature for a specific type of UAV RS operations is identified, the problem of Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions (FISR) is formulated and described in detail, and a novel method to deal with it is introduced.

As part of this work, a novel mCPP method, tailored to real-world UAV RS operations has been introduced, that supports very complex-shaped, non-convex ROIs, with additional no-fly-zones (NFZs) inside them, manages wisely the operational resources -like time and energy- and manages to achieve almost complete coverage in all cases. To realize that, an optimization scheme based on simulated annealing has been introduced, to efficiently apply grid-based path planning methodologies in real-world ROIs. Moreover, i) a heuristic is applied for Spanning Tree Coverage (STC) path planning method to reduce the number of turns in the generated trajectories, and ii) a modification to a state-of-the-art (SoA) method for area allocation is performed, to support proportional area division and enable the simultaneous utilization of heterogeneous vehicles. The introduced method is extensively evaluated through a series of simulated runs and a comparison with an alternative SoA method, a multi-agent marginal utility study is performed to provide information on how and when the deployment of multiple UAVs can benefit coverage missions, and two indicative real-world scenarios regarding precision agriculture and search and rescue (SAR) operations are deployed, collecting and processing data to provide relative results.

As a next step, building upon the aforementioned work, a CPP method with three ad-hoc coverage modes that intend to fulfill different objectives, each of them more appropriate for different applications, operational demands, and

vehicles, is introduced. This work focuses on resolving any remaining issues when applying grid-based path planning missions to real-world operations, and while the introduced heuristics are tailored to the STC method, this work can serve as a practical guide for most grid-based methods. The presented CPP solution is evaluated using the same simulation setup and benchmark ROIs as in the previous work, providing a direct comparison with it, and the alternative SoA method. The evaluations indicate that all claimed benefits are achieved, while simultaneously the method manages to overcome the issues inherited by its grid-based nature.

Finally, a new problem of UAVs' path planning for RS operations has been identified, described in detail, and resolved by introducing a novel method tailored to this purpose. The FISR problem -as stated above- is about the inspection of multiple disjoint ROIs with one or more UAVs, in the shortest amount of time possible, and the methodology that has been introduced to resolve it is the multi-UAV Disjoint Areas' Inspection (mUDAI). mUDAI deals with the FISR problem as two discrete optimization sub-problems, where i) the optimal viewpoints for capturing each defined ROI are calculated and ii) a set of trajectories that minimize time and respect the specifications and limitations of the vehicles used is generated. The introduced method is validated via two sets of real-world UAV deployments for FISR missions.

To enable easy and user-friendly deployment of UAVs for testing and evaluating the presented methodologies in real-world conditions, an end-to-end mission planning platform for RS operations has been developed. This platform, introduced in the first work and updated ever since, includes everything needed to design, store, manage, and deploy multi-UAV missions for RS operations with commercial devices.

The combination of SoA performance with increased levels of readiness and ease of use, makes steps towards closing the gap between commercial platforms that use simplistic approaches but provide robust and trusted solutions for real-world operations, and literature methods that introduce novel features and benefits, but are usually not ready or easy to deploy on field. Additionally, the development of solutions that allow the efficient and safe deployment of multiple UAVs working cooperatively to perform RS operations, contributes to overcome one of the major -at the moment- limitations of multi-copter UAVs, that is their limited operational duration. This way, the inspection of larger areas during the nominal operational duration of the vehicles is achieved, but also, time critical operations and applications that involve detecting moving objects of interest, are handled a lot more efficiently.

Στο πλαίσιο αυτής της διατριβής εξετάζεται το πρόβλημα του σχεδιασμού τροχιάς και δρομολόγησης για πολλαπλά μη επανδρωμένα εναέρια οχήματα (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles - UAVs), με στόχο την αποτελεσματική και αποδοτική εκτέλεση αποστολών τηλεπισκόπησης (Remote Sensing - RS). Το μεγαλύτερο τμήμα της παρούσας διατριβής επικεντρώνεται στο Σχεδιασμό Τροχιών Κάλυψης (Coverage Path Planning - CPP) και το Σχεδιασμό Τροχιών Κάλυψης με πολλαπλούς πράκτορες (multi-agent CPP - mCPP), δηλαδή το πρόβλημα της πλήρους κάλυψης μιας δεδομένης περιοχής ενδιαφέροντος (Region of Interest - ROI) με ένα ή περισσότερα UAVs, ενώ ταυτόχρονα τηρούνται οι περιορισμοί που μπορεί να επιβάλλονται από την περιοχή ενδιαφέροντος, τα οχήματα, τους χρήστες, καθώς επίσης και από τα επιχειρησιακά ή νομικά πλαίσια. Επιπλέον, εντοπίζεται ένα κενό στη βιβλιογραφία για έναν συγκεκριμένο τύπο επιχειρήσεων τηλεπισκόπησης με UAVs, διατυπώνεται, και περιγράφεται λεπτομερώς το πρόβλημα της Ταχείας Επιθεώρησης Διασκορπισμένων Περιοχών (Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions - FISR), και προτείνεται μια νέα μέθοδος για την αντιμετώπισή του.

Αρχικά, παρουσιάζεται μια νέα μέθοδος mCPP, προσανατολισμένη σε επιχειρήσεις τηλεπισκόπησης πραγματικού κόσμου με UAVs, η οποία υποστηρίζει πολύ σύνθετες, μη-κυρτές περιοχές ενδιαφέροντος με επιπλέον ζώνες απαγόρευσης πτήσης (No-Fly-Zones - NFZs) στο εσωτερικό τους, διαχειρίζεται με σύνεση τους επιχειρησιακούς πόρους -όπως ο χρόνος και η ενέργεια- και επιτυγχάνει σχεδόν πλήρη κάλυψη σε όλες τις περιπτώσεις. Για την επίτευξη αυτού του στόχου, εισάγεται ένα σχήμα βελτιστοποίησης βασισμένο στον αλγόριθμο Simulated Annealing για την αποτελεσματική εφαρμογή αλγορίθμων σχεδιασμού τροχιάς με βάση το πλέγμα (grid-based) σε πραγματικές περιοχές ενδιαφέροντος. Επιπλέον, ι) εφαρμόζεται μια ευρετική μέθοδος για τη μείωση των στροφών στις διαδρομές που παράγονται από τη μέθοδο Spanning Tree Coverage (STC), και ιι) πραγματοποιείται τροποποίηση μιας μεθόδου αιχμής (state-of-the-art - SoA) για το διαμοιρασμό περιοχών σε πολλαπλά ρομπότ, ώστε να υποστηρίζεται η αναλογική διάφιση των περιοχών και η ταυτόχρονη αξιοποίηση ετερογενών οχημάτων. Η προτεινόμενη μέθοδος αξιολογείται εκτενώς μέσω μιας σειράς προσομοιώσεων, συγκρίνεται με μια εναλλακτική μέθοδο αιχμής, ενώ πραγματοποιείται και μία με-

λέτη οριακής χρησιμότητας (marginal utility study) πολλαπλών πρακτόρων, για να προσδιοριστεί πότε και πώς η χρήση πολλαπλών UAVs μπορεί να είναι ωφέλιμη σε αποστολές κάλυψης περιοχών. Τέλος, εκτελούνται δύο ενδεικτικά σενάρια πραγματικού κόσμου, σχετικά με τη γεωργία ακριβείας και τις επιχειρήσεις έρευνας και διάσωσης, συλλέγονται δεδομένα, και επεξεργάζονται για την εξαγωγή και την παρουσίαση σχετικών αποτελεσμάτων.

Στη συνέχεια, βασισμένη στη δουλειά που περιγράφεται στην προηγούμενη παράγραφο παρουσιάζεται μια μέθοδος CPP με τρεις διακριτές λειτουργίες κάλυψης, με την κάθε μία να εξυπηρετεί καλύτερα διαφορετικές εφαρμογές, επιχειρησιακές απαιτήσεις και τύπους οχημάτων. Αυτή η δουλειά εστιάζει στην επίλυση των εναπομεινόντων ζητημάτων που προκύπτουν κατά την εφαρμογή μεθόδων σχεδιασμού διαδρομής με βάση το πλέγμα σε επιχειρήσεις πραγματικού κόσμου. Παρόλο που οι ευρετικές μέθοδοι που παρουσιάζονται και εφαρμόζονται είναι προσαρμοσμένες στα χαρακτηριστικά της μεθόδου STC, η δουλειά αυτή μπορεί να λειτουργήσει ως πρακτικός οδηγός για την επίλυση αντίστοιχων ζητημάτων στις περισσότερες μεθόδους με πλέγμα. Η λύση CPP που παρουσιάζεται, αξιολογείται χρησιμοποιώντας την ίδια μεθοδολογία και περιοχές αναφοράς με την προηγούμενη δουλειά, παρέχοντας άμεση σύγκριση με αυτήν και την εναλλακτική μέθοδο αιχμής. Η αξιολόγηση αποδεικνύει ότι επιτυγχάνονται όλα τα υποσχόμενα οφέλη, ενώ ταυτόχρονα η μέθοδος καταφέρνει να ξεπεράσει τα προβλήματα που απορρέουν από τη βασισμένη-σε-πλέγμα φύση της.

Τέλος, εντοπίζεται ένα νέο πρόβλημα σχεδιασμού διαδρομών UAVs για επιχειρήσεις τηλεπισκόπησης, το οποίο περιγράφεται λεπτομερώς και επιλύεται με την εισαγωγή μιας νέας μεθοδολογίας εστιασμένης στη βέλτιστη αντιμετώπισή του. Το πρόβλημα FISR -όπως αναφέρθηκε παραπάνω- αφορά την επίβλεψη πολλαπλών διακριτών περιοχών ενδιαφέροντος, με ένα ή περισσότερα UAVs, στο συντομότερο δυνατό χρόνο. Η μέθοδος που προτείνεται για την επίλυσή του είναι η Επιθεώρηση Διακριτών Περιοχών με Πολλαπλά UAVs (multi-UAV Disjoint Areas' Inspection - mUDAI). Η μέθοδος αυτή αντιμετωπίζει το πρόβλημα FISR ως δύο διακριτά υποπροβλήματα βελτιστοποίησης που αφορούν: i) τον υπολογισμό των βέλτιστων σημείων παρατήρησης για κάθε ορισμένη περιοχή ενδιαφέροντος και ii) τη δημιουργία διαδρομών που ελαχιστοποιούν το χρόνο και σέβονται τις προδιαγραφές και τους περιορισμούς των οχημάτων που χρησιμοποιούνται. Η προτεινόμενη μέθοδος αξιολογείται μέσω της εκτέλεσης δύο ομάδων αποστολών τηλεπισκόπησης για αποστολές FISR διαφορετικής κλίμακας, σε διαφορετικές τοποθεσίες.

Για την εύκολη εκτέλεση αποστολών με UAVs, και τη δοκιμή και αξιολόγηση των προτεινόμενων μεθοδολογιών σε πραγματικές συνθήκες, αναπτύχθηκε μια ολοκληρωμένη πλατφόρμα σχεδιασμού και εκτέλεσης αποστολών τηλεπισκόπησης. Αυτή η πλατφόρμα αναπτύχθηκε και παρουσιάστηκε κατά την πρώτη δουλειά αυτής της διατριβής και ενημερώνεται διαρκώς έκτοτε. Σε αυτήν περιλαμβάνονται όλα τα απαραίτητα στοιχεία για το σχεδιασμό, την αποθήκευση, τη διαχείριση και

την εκτέλεση αποστολών με πολλαπλά UAVs για επιχειρήσεις τηλεπισκόπησης με εμπορικές συσκευές.

Ο συνδυασμός χαρακτηριστικών αιχμής -όσον αφορά την αποτελεσματικότητα και αποδοτικότητα των αποστολών- με τα αυξημένα επίπεδα ετοιμότητας και ευχρηστίας, αποτελεί ένα βήμα προς την κάλυψη του κενού μεταξύ εμπορικών εφαρμογών που χρησιμοποιούν απλοϊκές προσεγγίσεις σχεδιασμού τροχιάς, αλλά παρέχουν αξιόπιστες λύσεις για πραγματικές επιχειρήσεις, και των μεθόδων της βιβλιογραφίας που εισάγουν καινοτόμα χαρακτηριστικά και οφέλη, αλλά συνήθως δεν είναι αρκετά ώριμες ή εύκολες για χρήση στον πραγματικό κόσμο. Επιπλέον, η ανάπτυξη λύσεων που επιτρέπουν την αποδοτική και ασφαλή χρήση πολλαπλών UAVs για την εκτέλεση αποστολών τηλεπισκόπησης, συμβάλλει στην υπέρβαση ενός από τους σημαντικότερους -αυτή τη στιγμή- περιορισμούς των εμπορικών UAVs, δηλαδή τη μικρή διάρκεια πτήσης τους. Με αυτόν τον τρόπο, καθίσταται εφικτή η σάρωση μεγαλύτερων περιοχών ενδιαφέροντος κατά τη διάρκεια της ονομαστικής επιχειρησιακής διάρκειας των οχημάτων, ενώ επίσης οι χρονικά κρίσιμες επιχειρήσεις, και οι εφαρμογές που περιλαμβάνουν τον εντοπισμό κινούμενων αντικειμένων ενδιαφέροντος, διαχειρίζονται πολύ πιο αποτελεσματικά.

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1

Introduction

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1.1 Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

The envision and initial steps towards the realization of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) date back to World War I, when the first attempts to deploy aerial torpedoes were made [1]. Since then, UAVs have seen unprecedented levels of growth, in both civilian and military applications, with several types of UAVs -having different size, range, flight and maneuver capabilities- being available in the market and able to conduct a wide range of operations. The major categories of commercial UAVs are: single-rotor, multi-rotor, fixed-wing and hybrid aircrafts with the capability of Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) [2]. During the past decade, these commercial UAVs have managed to achieve an impressive combination of affordability and functional capabilities, making them very popular among professionals as powerful platforms for performing various tasks, and acquiring data in a fast and efficient way. This trend has led to a rapid

market growth for enterprise aerial devices [3], incorporating application-oriented capabilities and advanced sensors.

1.1.1 Enterprise Applications

Some of the most popular domains that exploit UAVs for increased effectiveness and efficiency are: precision agriculture [4–6], infrastructure inspection [7–9], search and rescue (SAR) [10–12], post crisis monitoring and response [13–15], surveillance, and security monitoring [16–18]. In most of these fields, UAVs are used as platforms to collect high-quality data out of dedicated regions of interest (ROIs), or objects. However, there are also certain applications where the UAVs should perform some kind of task, instead of collecting data, as for example spraying agricultural fields [19, 20], or transporting items as a post-crisis first response action [21, 22].

1.1.2 Remote Sensing

The field of collecting information about objects, areas, or phenomena without making physical contact with them is defined as remote sensing (RS) [23]. It typically involves using sensors, mounted on static objects, or moving devices, to detect and measure various characteristics of the Earth’s surface, or designated objects. Depending on the sensor’s distance from the observed surface, RS devices have different scale and spatial resolution. The term scale refers to the amount of area captured in a single shot of the sensor. The larger the distance from ground, the larger the amount of area that will be captured by the sensor as well. On the other hand, spatial resolution refers to the level of detail in a sensor’s capture, and it describes the size of the area represented by each pixel. As shown in figure 1.1, based on the distance from ground, RS devices can be grouped in three categories: ground-based, airborne, and spaceborne.

UAVs belong to the lower level of RS devices, ranging from the lowest to the mid-lower of the airborne category, depending on their specific type (rotor, VTOL, winged, etc.). This means that the data collected by UAVs are on the higher end of spatial resolution, while the RS scale is on the lower range. As a result, UAVs are appropriate for applications that demand data with a high level of detail, and the areas that need to be covered are not very large. By collecting multiple sequential images with an overlap among them, it is feasible to apply processing techniques to generate high-resolution 2D and 3D maps of the scanned regions [24, 25]. This allows for RS operations of higher scale with UAVs, however, the time demanded to scan larger ROIs, along with the limited operational duration and range of UAVs, still enforce an upper limit on the amount of area that can be captured.

Figure 1.1. Remote sensing scale and levels based on sensor's distance from ground

Compared to ground-based RS devices, UAVs can capture data of larger areas, while still maintaining a very high spatial resolution. Moreover, unlike spaceborne devices, which have lower spatial resolution and are limited by weather, orbit, and schedule constraints, UAVs can provide a reliable on-demand RS solution, that can still operate under cloudiness and light rain, or snowfall¹. While in general the selection of the appropriate RS device and sensing level strongly depends on the objectives of each application, the undisputed advantages of UAVs in certain domains makes them a very popular solution among professionals, especially as new technical solutions enable additional features, and their ownership cost further decreases.

1.1.3 Automated and Autonomous Operations

Along with the increasing popularity of UAVs as enterprise RS platforms, the need of technical solutions to support and manage their operations has appeared. This demand has triggered the development of tools for automated guidance and autonomous navigation, and application-oriented data processing techniques, to efficiently and effortlessly achieve the desired objectives of their operations. The use of software solutions that automate UAV flights and data gathering, ensures consistent efficiency and effectiveness of the operations, while simultaneously

¹Depending on the specific device.

minimizes potential errors introduced by the human factor. Thanks to such solutions, UAVs can successfully conduct complex tasks without the presence of highly-trained pilots, spreading the benefits of their use to a wider audience.

The simplest approach to automate a flight is by allowing the operator to define a set of waypoints (locations on a map) for the UAV to visit, along with specific instructions for the data collection. To introduce optimality in this process, a solution to a Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) [26] can be calculated, providing the most efficient visitation order for the defined locations according to an optimization objective. If multiple vehicles are involved in the operation, in a similar approach, the solution to a Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) [27] can be used for the generation of optimal routes. Nevertheless, the most commonly used approach for UAVs' RS operations is a solution to a problem that is usually referred in literature as Coverage Path Planning (CPP) [28]. The CPP problem can be stated as follows: given a *defined ROI* and *specific coverage capabilities of the sensors or tools used*, provide paths, for one or more mobile robots, in order to *completely cover the ROI*, taking into account *spatial and motion constraints*. The use of coverage trajectories to scan a defined ROI ensures thorough data collection, that are appropriate for post-processing techniques generating representations of the regions. Given the objectives and specificities of each application, a combination of different methods, or even the development of fully custom techniques, is likely to be needed. Finally, for the deployment of UAVs in dynamically changing and evolving environments, or areas with unmapped obstacles, the use of appropriate sensors and on-board navigation algorithms enables a level of autonomy that is required to ensure safe operations.

The automation of UAV operations has also enabled the safe and efficient deployment of multiple unmanned vehicles, acting cooperatively to fulfill a common objective for a mission. Such multi-agent systems can provide several benefits in different applications, with the most important of them being i) the ability to overcome the limited energy capacity of the vehicles, allowing them to scan larger ROIs during their nominal operational duration, ii) the minimization of time needed to fulfill the objectives of a given task in time-critical operations, like SAR missions, and iii) the fact that deploying multiple sensors in different locations -at the same time- significantly increases the possibility of detection moving objects, when this is desired. The complexity of these multi-agent systems, along with the challenges that need to be faced to allow for efficient, but most of all safe operations, have triggered the interest of many researchers during the past years, and has led to several works that follow different approaches, and face the problem from different perspectives [29–31].

Taking the aforementioned into consideration, it is rational that several commercial and open-source solutions for the automation of UAV flights are

available. Usually, the commercial solutions use simpler, but tested and mature path planning approaches, while the research works push the boundaries to increase the operational effectiveness and efficiency, in a generic, or application-oriented manner. Some of the most popular mission planning applications and platforms -at the moment this dissertation is written- are: Ardupilot Mission Planner², DJI Flight Planner³, Drone Harmony⁴ and Pix4DCapture⁵. Furthermore, a comprehensive literature review, focusing on the most relevant for the content of this dissertation research works, is included in the following chapter.

1.2 Motivation and Contributions

By studying the relevant literature and using the available mission planning platforms, one can identify that there is a relatively large gap between them, in terms of: i) maturity level and ease of use, and ii) efficiency and effectiveness of the trajectory planning solutions. This is usually caused by the fact that platforms prioritize robustness and maturity level over efficiency, while several research works that claim increased effectiveness, make assumptions to simplify the faced problem, and perform evaluations in simulated setups that do not account for factors and challenges met in real-world operations. Moreover, few-to-none platforms allow for multi-UAV deployment, and those that do, usually use simplistic approaches that do not provide increased levels of safety and efficiency.

The main focus of this dissertation is to close the gap between the maturity of simplistic path planning approaches met in commercial mission planners, and the effectiveness and efficiency of SoA solutions, that are usually not steady or mature enough for trustworthy real-world operations. Great effort has been given towards providing safe and efficient multi-UAV path planning solutions, that manage to overcome common issues and challenges met on the field, in RS missions. By introducing optimization techniques, heuristics, and identifying path planning problems stemming from new needs in UAVs' RS operations, novel path planning techniques, for efficient multi-UAV RS missions are introduced. Moreover, the development and use of custom software and hardware setups, has allowed the real-world testing and validation of these newly introduced methods. It is worth mentioning that, while each of the path planning solutions presented in this dissertation are applicable -with minor-to-no modifications- to different kinds of manned or unmanned vehicles and devices, for various

²<http://ardupilot.org/planner>, accessed on 10 November 2024

³<https://www.djiflightplanner.com>, accessed on 10 November 2024

⁴<https://droneharmony.com>, accessed on 10 November 2024

⁵<https://www.pix4d.com/product/pix4dcapture>, accessed on 10 November 2024

tasks and applications, the major objective during their development was the optimization of multi-UAV, real-world RS operations.

The key contributions of this dissertation are outlined below:

- Introduction of optimization techniques and heuristics for the efficient -in terms of achieved coverage and used operational resources- deployment of grid-based path planning approaches in real-world operations.
- Modification of a SoA method for area allocation in multi-agent CPP operations [32], to support proportional area division and allow the simultaneous use of heterogeneous vehicles.
- These contributions have enabled the development of a highly efficient, deployment-ready method for mutli-UAV coverage operations, that supports complex-shaped, non-convex ROIs, with additional no-fly-zones (NFZ) inside it.
- Extensive simulated and real-world evaluation and testing of the multi-agent CPP (mCPP) solution, including a comparison with a SoA method, and a multi-agent marginal utility study to explain and quantify the actual benefits of deploying multiple UAVs on the field.
- Introduction and extensive evaluation of three ad-hoc coverage modes, that build upon the introduced mCPP solution, to further increase operational effectiveness in an application-oriented manner.
- Identification and thorough definition of a new path planning problem for the Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions (FISR) with UAVs.
- Introduction of a novel method that provides an efficient solution to the FISR problem, named multi-UAV Disjoint Areas Inspection (mUDAI).
- Extensive real-world evaluation of the mUDAI method, including a comparison with an alternative path planning solution for the objectives of the FISR problem.
- Introduction of an end-to-end platform for efficient and effective mutli-UAV remote sensing operations.

1.3 Dissertation Outline

The rest of this dissertation is organized as follows: Chapter 2 provides a detailed overview of recent research works related to this topic. Chapter 3 introduces a novel mutli-UAV coverage mission planning platform for efficient real-world

RS operations. Chapter 4 builds upon the work presented in chapter 3, to solve the remaining issues, and provide solutions for the effective deployment of grid-based path planning approaches in real-world conditions in general. Chapter 5 identifies and defines in detail the FISR problem, and proposes mUDAI methodology to solve it. Chapter 6 presents the conclusions and future work plans. Finally, appendix A shortly presents the Spanning Tree Coverage (STC) algorithm [33], that is necessary for the understanding of chapters 3 and 4, and appendix B presents the software setup that has allowed the real-world deployment of UAV missions for the testing and validation of the presented path planning solutions.

2

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In literature, over the years, numerous research works have been presented on the automation of unmanned vehicles' missions in general, and UAVs' missions in particular. This section shortly presents some of the most influential, and some of the most recent research works, related to the content of this dissertation. The presented works have been organized in three sections, following the structure introduced in the previous chapter. Specifically, section 2.1 is about the optimal routing of one or more vehicles, section 2.2 is about CPP and mCPP methods, and section 2.3 is about combinatorial methods, focusing on what is usually called TSP-CPP in literature. Out of those sections, the one regarding CPP is the most extensive, as it is the thematic section that occupies the largest part of this dissertation as well.

2.1 Traveling Salesman and Vehicle Routing Problems

In computational complexity theory, the TSP [26] is about finding the shortest possible route that visits a given set of cities exactly once and returns to the

starting point, based on the distances between each pair of cities. It is a classic NP-hard problem in combinatorial optimization [34], making it one of the most challenging and extensively studied topics in theoretical computer science and operations research. TSP has numerous practical applications, such as optimizing delivery routes [35–37], designing efficient circuit boards [38, 39], and managing supply chain logistics [40–42]. Despite its straightforward formulation, solving TSP efficiently for large datasets remains a significant challenge, emphasizing its importance in exploring the boundaries of computational efficiency and algorithm design. VRP [43] is a generalization of the TSP problem, and deals with the same challenge, however this time for a fleet of vehicles that need to perform deliveries to a given set of customers. Over the years, both TSP and VRP have been adjusted and used to a wide range of operations, including -in the recent past years- the efficient routing of UAVs that need to visit a set of predefined locations. Below, some indicative, recent research works about efficient UAVs' routing, are presented.

One of the most popular scenarios where UAV flights are automated with the use of TSP, involves the transportation and delivery of parcels to predefined locations. Various approaches have been introduced, and many of them involve combining UAVs and trucks to provide a solution with real-world value, as far as operational duration and range are concerned. This variation of the problem is usually referred as Traveling Salesman Problem with Drones (TSP-D). [44] is about deliveries with one UAV that is carried by one truck, and introduces an integer programming model for the TSP-D problem, solving medium-size instances optimally. The paper offers a worst-case approximation guarantee, compares heuristics with exact solutions, and assesses drone delivery performance across various scenarios, showing significant time savings over truck-only delivery. Building upon the same concept, [45] allows the truck to launch and pick the UAV from locations that do not correspond to the depot or delivery positions, but are along the route, [46] deals with the optimal customer assignments for a UAV working in cooperation with a traditional delivery truck, and [47, 48] introduce approaches to improve the quality of the solution and the delivery efficiency, with significant time reduction potentials. [49] goes one step forward and allows the cooperation of one truck with more than one UAVs, introducing the TSP with multiple Drones (TSP-mD), while [50, 51] deal with the multiple TSP-D (mTSP-D), which is about n trucks cooperating with m UAVs to perform deliveries. Of course, there are also research works that deal with the UAVs' routing for delivery tasks, without the presence of trucks [52–54], trying to deal with various aspects and challenges of this operation.

The close enough TSP (CETSP) [55] is a variant of the TSP, where the vehicle is allowed to approach the predefined locations, without actually reaching the exact positions. This variation can be applied in UAV monitoring, tracking

and filming tasks, since the field of view (FoV) of the sensor allows collecting data from the exact desired locations without reaching them. This approach helps to shorten the path and reduce the time of a certain task, allowing the UAV to visit more locations during its nominal operational duration. [56] deals with this problem, validating the proposed solution with simulated experiments.

Another application that can involve UAV routing is engineering management, where UAVs are used for inspection purposes in high-risk construction sites, providing a highly efficient method for identifying hidden risks. [57] addresses the optimization of UAV inspection routing and scheduling, accounting for challenges like NFZs, time-windows (TWs), and multiple monitoring rounds. A mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model is proposed to optimize task assignments, schedules, and charging decisions. Due to the complexity of large-scale instances, a customized variable neighborhood search metaheuristic is developed for efficient problem-solving. Similarly, [58] proposes a method for off-shore wind farm inspections with UAVs, to reduce the demanded time, man-hours, and exposure of workers to risk. The authors formulate a placement optimization problem that minimizes the number of demanded UAVs, and a routing optimization problem that minimizes the inspection time, taking into account the wind's speed that affects the flying range and speed. Finally, [59] presents an approach similar to the TSP-mD presented above, however, this time as a vehicle-assisted routing solution for UAVs' inspections. By introducing a regular vehicle, the authors intend to overcome the operational duration limitation of the UAVs, and by utilizing more than one UAVs, that can be launched and retrieved in different locations, they minimize the time wastage for both the regular vehicle and the UAVs.

It should be noted that in several of the works presented above, the maximum flight time of UAVs is identified as a limitation, that the authors try to mitigate or overcome by i) increasing the operational efficiency of the generated routes, ii) utilizing multiple UAVs to increase the tasking capability during this duration, or iii) assisting the UAV operations with regular ground vehicles to retrieve them, recharge them, and deploy them again.

2.2 Coverage Path Planning

Given that CPP provides a powerful tool for a wide range of domains and applications, it has attracted a great interest over the years and there are many research works about it. The state-of-the-art on CPP methods for robotics in general is summarized in [28], and works tailored to UAVs are presented in [60].

CPP methods can be divided in categories according to different criteria that focus on specific aspects of the problem. The most important of them are:

1. *exact/approximate cellular decomposition* -with *grid-based* methods being a very popular sub-category of the approximate decomposition ones- based on how the method discretizes the ROI in order to calculate trajectories,
2. *single/multi-agent* methods, regarding the number of agents (robots, vehicles, etc.) that can participate in a mission,
3. *on-line/off-line* methods, based on whether or not an on-going mission can be adjusted by getting real-time feedback from the operational area,
4. and *energy-aware* or *not*, based on whether some actions are taken in order to provide energy-efficient paths (e.g., reduce turns and overall length, avoid redundant scans etc.).

In addition to them, there are also different categories regarding the patterns of paths that come out. The most dominant of them are:

1. the ones using *lawnmower patterns*, that are simple back-and-forth patterns with a defined distance between them,
2. *Spanning Tree Coverage* (STC) [33] *patterns*, where a Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) [61] is constructed at first and a path that circumnavigates the MST is generated afterwards,
3. and methods using *spiral patterns*, navigating from a sided starting point to a centrally-placed ending point of the ROI, or reverse.

This section presents an overview of influential, and relatively recent CPP works, highlighting their functionalities, features, and shortcomings. Table 2.1 presents an overview of the works included in this section. Furthermore, in the end of the section, some additional grid-based approaches of high-interest are included, and issues inherited by their nature are discussed.

One of the most popular approaches in the CPP problem is the boustrophedon cellular decomposition [62]. This method generates lawnmower patterns and was initially designed in an attempt to minimize the number of excess lengthwise motions of the robot. An important advantage of the method, making it so popular, is the fact that it can be used for complex-shaped ROIs with NFZs inside them, providing very high percentage of coverage. Many works so far are based on it, exploiting certain aspects, improving and extending this approach. Some recent examples that exploit boustrophedon cellular decomposition are: [64] where the authors present a method to define and calculate flight times in a boustrophedon aerial survey coverage path in wind, for precision agriculture applications and [65] which is introduced by the authors as a semi-boustrophedon method, because, while they use boustrophedon cellular decomposition, they

Method	Real-life experiments	Multi-agent support	Task allocation	Integrated platform	Supported shape of ROI	Support of NFZ/Obstacles
[62], [63]	✗	✗	-	✗	Convex & Concave polygons	✓
[64]	✗	✗	-	✗	Convex & Concave polygons	✓*
[65]	✗	✗	-	✗	Convex & Concave Non-connective ROIs	✓
[66]	✓	✗	-	ROS implementation	Convex & Concave polygons	✓
[67]	✓	✗	-	✗	Convex polygons	✗
[68]	✗	✓	Exclusive & Proportional	✗	Convex polygons	✗
[33, 69]	✗	✗	-	✗	Grid with obstacle cells	✓- obstacle cells
[70, 71]	✗	✓	Single path allocation based on initial positions	✗	Grid with obstacle cells	✓- obstacle cells
[72]	✗	✓	Non-exclusive single path allocation	✗	Grid with obstacle cells	✓- obstacle cells
[32]	✗	✓	Exclusive Equal	✗	Grid with obstacle cells	✓- obstacle cells
[73]	✗	✓	Exclusive & Equal	✗	Multi-scale grid with obstacles	✓- obstacle cells
[74]	✓	✓	Minimum overlap & Proportional after negotiation	✓	Convex & Concave polygons	✓
[75]	✓	✓	Minimum overlap	✗	Convex & Concave polygons	✓**

Table 2.1. *Overview of CPP methods*

*Not explicitly mentioned in the paper, but this feature is supported inherently by the method used.

**In the paper NFZs are only included between the home position of the UAVs and the first mission’s waypoint, but not inside the ROI.

do not limit coverage strictly to boustrophedon paths in order to reduce runtime, while maintaining near-optimal path length. This family of approaches is the most commonly used for real-life operations, at the moment, because of its incorporated advantages and its out-of-the-box adaptability to complex-shaped ROIs. However, it is not the most energy-efficient one, as it many times includes redundant movements that do not contribute to the scanning procedure (e.g., from the starting/ending points to the home position of the vehicles) and multiple times re visitation of certain points, to ensure complete coverage.

In [63] exact cellular decomposition method is used in order to provide turn-minimized paths for UAVs inside a polygon ROI. It is shown that this kind of paths is more efficient, as turns are time and energy consuming for UAV missions. In this work, convex or concave polygon regions are decomposed to convex sub-regions. After that, the optimal path orientation for every sub-region is calculated and sub-regions get connected again, to provide the overall path. While this work becomes a lot more energy-efficient by significantly reducing the number of turns, it still inherits the issues mentioned in the previous paragraph.

[66] presents one relatively recent work, where boustrophedon CPP [62] is extended in order to find the optimal sweeping direction for every sub-region of a user-defined ROI, including obstacles and NFZs. This method exploits already existing approaches on combination and manages to attract the interest as one of the most appropriate for real-life use implementations of coverage mission planners. It was developed for low-altitude flights with UAVs, and is available in an open-source robot operating system (ROS) implementation. The mission planner presented in this work, outperforms in terms of time-efficiency and ability to handle NFZs many existing -commercial or not- planners available at the moment (as the ones mention in chapter 1). A point that this work falls short, is that it cannot handle multiple UAVs missions.

In [67] a CPP method tailored to UAVs, having in mind real-life problems and limitations faced in photogrammetry applications, is presented. In this work an energy model derived from real measurements is introduced, that is used to provide a power consumption estimation for the UAV. After that, an energy aware algorithm is proposed, that provides path with reduced energy consumption, while taking into account image resolution constraints. On the top of that, two safety mechanisms are presented. The first one, executed off-line, checks if the available energy is enough to complete a calculated mission, while the second, on-line mechanism, reassures safe return for the UAV to the take-off location, in case the remaining battery energy is not enough to complete a mission and return to home. While this work manages to efficiently face some of the challenges that are met in real-life operations, it still remains limited by the UAV's battery life, as it cannot handle multiple UAVs in the same mission.

[68] presents a mCPP method for UAVs. The introduced algorithm divides the ROI into smaller, exclusive sub-regions for every UAV and computes a turn-minimized back and forth path for every UAV, inside their exclusive sub-regions. Although this work presents an interesting approach, it can only handle convex polygon areas and does not support NFZs inside them.

Another popular approach in the CPP domain is STC method [33]. STC subdivides the operational area into disjoint cells, which are used for the generation of a spanning tree. As a next step, a path is generated around this spanning tree and the method guarantees that every point of the grid is covered precisely once.

This circumnavigating path has the advantage of avoiding redundant movements of the robot, that do not contribute in the scanning procedure. A mission starts and ends in the same position and every cell is visited only once. This way, the paths generated are highly appropriate for energy-efficient applications. Defining obstacles inside a ROI is also supported, by removing connections of nodes that represent them, during the MST generation. However, being a grid based method, it can turn out to be inefficient for covering complex-shaped ROIs, because of common discretization issues [76, 77]. As in boustrophedon approach, there are also a lot of works based on STC, exploiting certain aspects and extending this approach, such as [69] where the authors attempt to extended spanning tree based coverage (X-STC) algorithm, in order to cover even the partially occupied cells, which helps in the better coverage of complex-shaped polygon regions. As also mentioned in introduction, STC is of great importance for the understanding of this dissertation, and for this reason a short presentation of the method is included in appendix A.

In addition, [70–72] present some approaches expanding the STC for multi-agent use. [70] is the first approach utilizing STC for the mCPP problem, and [71, 72] introduce ideas to solve it more efficiently. In all of these works, a single MST is constructed and the generated path around it gets allocated proportionally to the multiple robots. This approach for multi-agent coverage though, is not the most efficient one, as the portion of the area that will be allocated to each robot is dependent on their initial positions, ignoring the operational capabilities of each member of the team. Moreover, there are cases where the same cell of the grid has to be scanned multiple times by different members. Finally, it should be noted that none of these works include real-life applications.

[32] is also a STC-based approach that deals with the mCPP problem, for grids with prior-defined obstacles. However, this work approaches the problem from a completely different point of view, compared to [70–72]. Specifically, [32] deals with the multiple vehicles, by reducing the mCPP problem to, as-many-as-the-number-of-robots single-robot CPP problems. This is achieved by the division of the overall ROI to equal, exclusive sub-regions for each vehicle, based on their initial positions. The proposed methodology promises to always converge to a solution, at least in cases where one exists, and also offers a significantly reduced complexity compared to other SoA approaches of that time. While [32] presents a really promising approach, it does not contain any real-life experiments that would validate its real-world efficiency.

Based on a different approach, where an overall region is divided in exclusive sub-regions and then allocated to a group of UAVs, [73] identifies the gap of coverage path planning in complex geographic environments and proposes an STC-based mCPP method, called M CCP-MLCT. This method constructs a

grid with multiple scales (different sizes of cells), based on the complexity and topology of the environment that will be applied. The key idea is that different parts of a ROI that should be covered, should be faced in different ways, e.g., in a search and rescue task, more complex parts of the region should be scanned in more detail, so smaller-sized cells should be used for the construction of MSTs. This work introduces an idea that makes it highly appropriate for specific types of missions, where the detail of collected data should vary depending on the environment characteristics. While an application of the CPP method is presented for a real remote sensing image, this work does not include any real-life experiments.

An integrated platform for managing missions for precision agriculture, utilizing multiple UAVs, is presented in [74]. This work contains a complete top-to-down approach, as it describes a tool containing everything from a graphic user interface (GUI) on a ground station, to a robust flight controller for the UAVs, to improve their maneuverability. The main contribution here is the practical experimentation with an integrated tool, however a new one-phase task partitioning manager is presented and a CPP method that minimizes turns and times of revisiting a specific cell is used as well. It is worth pointing out that this setup is able to handle non-convex ROIs with NFZs inside them as well. Even if there are available more energy-efficient approaches for the coverage paths generation, this work is one of the most complete, in terms of integration level for the presented platform.

Another work, including real-life, multi-UAV operations, under very harsh weather conditions, is presented in [75]. The authors have developed a mCPP methodology based on a completely different approach, in order to face a set of challenges that are met in surveys of penguin colonies in Antarctica. The main objective of this work is to minimize the time duration of the missions, a factor that is critical for this type of operations. The proposed methodology, named Path Optimization for Population Counting with Overhead Robotic Networks (POPCORN), generates paths for multiple UAVs by solving a series of satisfiability modulo theory (SMT) instances (high-level objectives are defined at this step, e.g., same or almost same starting and ending positions for the paths). By iteratively reducing the maximum allowed path's length, this methodology manages to calculate the shortest possible paths to completely cover a ROI. The backtracking of paths and the places revisited by multiple UAVs is minimal, but still not null, however in missions where detecting moving targets is desired, this could not be considered as a disadvantage.

Out of the works presented above, [32, 33, 69–75] are grid-based. This means that these methodologies use a grid as a guide for the generation of the coverage trajectories. As a result, the provided paths intend to completely cover the representation of the ROI on grid, which -depending on the specific method- can

significantly deviate from the actual ROI. Some additional grid-based approaches of high-interest are presented in [78–84]. While several of these works are applied -or at least easily applicable- to real-world scenarios, the lack of quantitative coverage evaluation for the methods does not provide any clue on how the ROIs' shape deviation affects their real-world effectiveness. In addition to that, while many of them allow the definition of NFZs inside the ROI, the generation of strictly geo-fenced paths (either regarding the ROI, or the NFZs) is a matter that does not seem to particularly concern the domain's researchers. Overall, although several interesting ideas are presented in the recent grid-based CPP works, almost none of them deals with the efficient representation of the ROI on grid first. This way, the introduced features apply to the representation of the ROI on grid, and not the actual user-defined region.

As a general conclusion from the CPP literature, many methods suffer in handling concave ROIs and NFZs, not all of them are capable of utilizing multiple vehicles, and extremely few are presented as integrated platforms for real-life use. Taking also into consideration that most (commercial) mission-planning platforms mostly use simple back-and-forth patterns, do not manage efficiently operational resources such as time and energy, and rarely support multi-UAV operations, there seems to be a significant gap between them and SoA approaches, in terms of real-world applicability, operational effectiveness, and efficiency.

2.3 Combinatorial Methods

Given the targeted objectives of a UAV deployment mission, it is likely that more established or traditional path planning approaches will not suffice to achieve the desired results. In several approaches though, a combination of methodologies like the ones described above, manages to provide a solution able to perform more complex tasks, and achieve the desired operational objectives. This subsection focused on the combination of TSP/VRP and CPP methodologies, for different operations and targeted applications.

[85] introduces an innovative, two-stage UAV path planning approach for precision agriculture, and [86] incorporates this novel scheme as part of an end-to-end platform for real-world operations. This system is designed to optimize field coverage while considering irregular-shaped ROIs, NFZs, and UAV limitations like battery life. The system employs a STC-based CPP algorithm, that intends to comprehensively scan the designated ROI, collect data, and analyze them. It also incorporates energy-aware features, minimizing unnecessary scanning redundancy, and travel times. By processing the collected data, a crop health monitoring procedure takes place, and the “problematic” areas are identified

and localized. As a second stage mission, a “hot-point mission” takes place, where a TSP problem is solved to identify the most efficient visitation order for the problematic areas, and a circular flight around these locations is performed. Experimental validation demonstrated that the generated paths effectively adapt to diverse field shapes, achieve high coverage percentages, reduce mission time, and provide extensive results of the problematic areas, highlighting the system’s capability to support real-world agricultural applications.

On the other hand, in a slightly different approach, there is a set of methods that combine TSP/VRP and CPP, in a single-stage mission, with the concept of performing coverage operations in more than one ROIs efficiently, during a single UAV(s) deployment mission. This problem is usually referred in literature as TSP-CPP, and some relatively recent research works have dealt with it. In the following paragraph, some of these works that manage to attract the interest, are presented.

[87] deals with TSP-CPP, providing a mixed integer programming formulation for the TSP problem at first, and dealing with the coverage of the separate ROIs as a next step. This work uses a simple back-and-forth scanning pattern for the coverage trajectories, and the evaluation of the method is performed in simulations. While relatively simplistic, the combination of these widespread approaches provides an efficient solution for the coverage of multiple disjoint regions, in a single UAV flight. However, the authors do not consider for real-world factors, limitations, and specifications of a typical UAV, not providing the readers with a realistic scale of operations that can be carried out, in terms of operational range and regions’ areas. [88] also deals with the problem of CPP in disjoint ROIs, however, in this case utilizing multiple UAVs for the coverage procedure. The authors approach it as a mix of multiple TSP (mTSP) and CPP, also considering the energy constraints of the UAVs and performing checks for each of the generated trajectories. This way, the work presented on this paper seems to identify the limited operational duration of the UAVs as a problem, and tries to overcome it by deploying multiple UAVs that perform the same task simultaneously. Once again here, the validation of the method is performed through simulations, and several real-world factors that can affect the real-world UAV deployment seem to be neglected. Finally, in [89] the authors approach the same problem in a slightly different way. Specifically, a scheme is proposed where the spiral pattern CPP is used as the core method, equal task assignment for the UAVs is performed, where each task may involve more than one ROIs, and a TSP problem is finally solved to find the most efficient order for the UAVs to visit the disjoint regions. The proposed method is designed for photovoltaic panels’ inspection use, however, in this work as well, the evaluation is performed in simulations.

2.4 Literature Study Conclusion

Overall, from the works presented above it is clear that there is a major issue, which several researchers try to resolve by applying different approaches. This issue is present in different types of operations and applications, and is caused by the limited operational duration of UAVs. Several methods try to overcome this problem by increasing the operational efficiency, extending this way the tasking capability of a single UAV in the same amount of time as well, or by proposing methods that deploy multiple UAVs at the same time, to cooperatively perform a specific task, allowing users extend the tasking capability by deploying additional vehicles on the field. Moreover, it is easy to identify a gap in many of the research works, that do not perform real-life experimentation and validation of the methods, neglecting (some times by choice) factors that can affect, or hinder, the field deployment of their proposed methods.

3

Cooperative Multi-UAV Coverage Mission Planning Platform for RS Operations

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3.1 Introduction

The work presented in this chapter deals with the mCPP problem, a problem that has been proven to be NP-hard when trying to solve optimally, in terms of minimal coverage time [72]. Multi-agent operations allow the conduction

of specific tasks in a significantly reduced amount of time, but also make possible the conduction of tasks that were previously not possible due to the limited operational duration of most commercial, multi-copter UAVs (20-50 min). Moreover, in this work great effort has been given to overcome some of the challenges that are faced when trying to apply any grid-based CPP methodology to real-world operations. The most important of these challenges are the incomplete coverage caused by discretization issues (extensively explained in sub-section 3.2.2), and the integration of features that make a methodology, at least efficient enough, to be used for real-world operations (e.g., turns, and paths' length reduction, minimal energy consumption, etc.). The mCPP methodology presented in this chapter, has been integrated to an end-to-end mission planning platform (see also appendix B) -developed from scratch- that intends to make a step towards the direction of combining SoA performance and features, with the ease of use provided by commercial mission planners when deploying UAV missions. This high-level, user-friendly platform, is able to perform multi-UAV coverage missions for remote sensing tasks, optimized for real-world use, and integrating energy-aware features.

3.1.1 Contributions

Overall, to achieve the aforementioned, in the context of this work:

1. A previous work from our lab [32] for multi-robot task allocation and coverage operations, is adjusted and applied for real-world use with UAVs. Specifically, [32] is extended to also support proportional allocation of the ROI to the vehicles, and great effort has been given to address some of the efficiency issues that arise when applying grid-based CPP methodologies in real-world operations.
2. A novel optimization procedure that significantly increases the percentage of coverage, and improves the qualitative features of the generated paths -for STC-based methods- is implemented and evaluated.
3. An approach to further reduce the path turns, and increase the energy-awareness of the proposed method is applied.
4. A comparison with a recent, powerful in terms of complete coverage and support of complex-shaped ROIs, SoA approach is performed, in order to quantify and evaluate the achieved performance of the resulting path planning scheme.
5. A multi-agent marginal utility study is performed, in order to investigate the actual efficiency gains that are introduced by the utilization of multiple UAVs, in coverage missions.

6. A new, end-to-end interface is developed, to provide a user-friendly interaction layer to create, perform, and manage missions (described in appendix B).
7. A robust communication interface to integrate with ease commercial UAVs to the platform is developed (also described in appendix B).
8. Two real-world experiments are performed, to demonstrate the applicability, and robustness of the developed platform in some indicative use cases.

The result of this work is a powerful multi-UAV mission planner, that supports no-fly-zones and obstacles in coverage operations, manages wisely the operational resources, supports both fair and proportional task allocation for the UAVs, depending on their operational capabilities, is easy to use, and is compatible with almost any commercial UAV, not demanding special and expensive equipment. Based on the categories that were mentioned in section 2.2, the proposed CPP methodology can be described as a grid-based, off-line, STC-pattern, multi-agent, energy aware solution. Figure 3.1 shows a mission example from the introduced platform, involving 10 UAVs, in a non-convex, complex-shaped polygon ROI with 2 NFZs, and the objective to completely cover the defined region, utilizing all UAVs equally.

3.1.2 Chapter Outline

The work presented in this chapter is organized as follows: section 3.2 presents the task allocation and coverage path planning methods, along with the optimization procedure that is implemented, in section 3.3 is performed a simulated evaluation of the proposed methodology, to assess the optimization procedure and the overall CPP efficiency, as well as a simulated multi-agent study, section 3.4 includes two different applications of the proposed platform in real-world experiments, along with visual results, and finally in 3.5 a summary of this work is included.

3.2 multi-agent Coverage Path Planning

In order to cope with the challenges that are faced in real-world, multi-UAV, coverage missions, it is essential to utilize an approach that (i) provides safe and efficient paths, (ii) respects the operational capabilities and motion-limitations of the vehicles, and (iii) ensures a high percentage of coverage, so as to gather sufficient information for any operational area. To efficiently address these issues, an optimized for real-world use mCPP method, based on a previous work of our lab [32], is proposed. In this chapter, the overall proposed method is described

Figure 3.1. Coverage mission with the proposed *mCPP* platform

The objective of this mission is to completely cover a non-convex, complex-shaped polygon ROI, that includes two separate NFZs inside it (marked with light-red color), involving 10 UAVs, that all contribute equally to the scanning procedure.

in detail, along with the optimizations that take place to make it appropriate and efficient for the multi-UAV domain.

The proposed *mCPP* method deals with the problem of designing paths for a team of UAVs, participating in a mission, given:

- a *user-defined polygon ROI*, probably including smaller polygon sub-regions representing NFZs/obstacles (O), formatted in the WGS84 (World Geodetic System - 1984) coordinate system [90], as follows:

$$\text{ROI} = \{(\text{lat}_1, \text{lon}_1), \dots, (\text{lat}_n, \text{lon}_n)\} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{O} = \{ \{(\text{lat}_{\text{ob}_1|1}, \text{lon}_{\text{ob}_1|1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{\text{ob}_1|n_1}, \text{lon}_{\text{ob}_1|n_1})\}, \dots, \{(\text{lat}_{\text{ob}_m|1}, \text{lon}_{\text{ob}_m|1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{\text{ob}_m|n_m}, \text{lon}_{\text{ob}_m|n_m})\} \} \quad (3.2)$$

where n is the count of polygon vertices, ob_i ($i = 0, \dots, m$) stands for the obstacle number (pointer), n_i ($i = 0, \dots, m$) is the count of vertices for each NFZ region and m the count of NFZs/obstacles.

- the *desired scanning density* (d_s) for the mission, in meters, representing the distance between two sequential trajectories,
- the *number of UAVs* (v_n) that will participate in the mission

- and the *initial positions of the UAVs* in the operational area (could be real, user-defined, or random), formatted in WGS84 as well:

$$\text{init}_{\text{pos}} = \{(\text{lat}_{v_1}, \text{lon}_{v_1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{v_{v_n}}, \text{lon}_{v_{v_n}})\} \quad (3.3)$$

where v_i ($i = 1, \dots, v_n$) stands for the UAV number (pointer).

As an output of the method, a set of paths, one path for each UAV participating in the mission, is produced, so as to provide complete coverage of the ROI:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{paths} = & \{ \{(\text{lat}_{v_1|1}, \text{lon}_{v_1|1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{v_1|m_1}, \text{lon}_{v_1|m_1})\}, \\ & \dots, \{(\text{lat}_{v_{v_n}|1}, \text{lon}_{v_{v_n}|1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{v_{v_n}|m_{v_n}}, \text{lon}_{v_{v_n}|m_{v_n}})\} \} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

where m_i ($i = 1, \dots, v_n$) is the count of waypoints for each UAV. Figure 3.2 presents the data-flow of the method.

Figure 3.2. Data-flow of the mCPP method

3.2.1 Field Representation on Grid

Transformation of Coordinates

As a first step, the input coordinates of the polygon ROI (4.6), the obstacles (3.2), and the UAVs' positions (3.3), are transformed from the WGS84 system, to a local NED (North East Down) system [90], with a common reference point inside the ROI. The reason why NED coordinate system is preferable, is because coordinates are represented in a local Cartesian system with the metric system being straight in meters. NED coordinates facilitate in the node placement and optimization procedures that are described below. The paths are also calculated in NED coordinates, and have to be transformed back to the WGS84 coordinate system, before given as output.

Nodes Placement

As a first step, the user-defined ROI must be represented on a grid. The grid size needs to be proportional to the user-defined scanning density - d_s . The center of every grid's cell represents a node which will be later used for the MST construction, with the actual path being laid around the constructed spanning tree. Therefore, the nodes in the grid should be placed with a distance of $d_n = 2 \times d_s$ between each other, in order to achieve the desired distance between trajectories.

To define the size of the grid, a bounding box around the polygon is constructed, as shown in 3.3(a) (red box). According to this, the grid size will be $x \times y$, where:

$$x = \lfloor \frac{x_{\max_p} - x_{\min_p}}{d_n} \rfloor \quad (3.5)$$

$$y = \lfloor \frac{y_{\max_p} - y_{\min_p}}{d_n} \rfloor \quad (3.6)$$

and $\lfloor r \rfloor$ denotes the floor of r (largest integer below the given real number).

After that, the $x \times y$ nodes are placed inside the bounding box with a d_n distance between each other.

Grid Representation

At this point, each one of the previously placed nodes should obtain a state that describes how it should be treated during the path generation procedure. The three possible states for every node are:

- *Obstacle*, used to represent areas that are outside of polygon, or inside NFZs. These nodes will not be used for the MST construction and no path will be laid around them.
- *Free Space*, used to represent nodes that will be used for MST construction and path generation.
- *UAV*, used to represent the initial UAVs' position.

Two different approaches are implemented to decide whether a node will be labeled as *Obstacle* or *Free Space*. Figures 3.3(b), 3.3(c) show an example of a polygon ROI representation on grid, using both approaches. The first one intends to provide *paths strictly inside the polygon* handling the boundaries of the polygon as a strict geo-fencing zone, while the second one allows paths to get outside of polygon, in order to provide even better coverage of the ROI. For the first approach, the characterization of a node comes out of the area around the node. Specifically, a check is performed, regarding whether the centers of all

(a) Standard and augmented bounding boxes

(b) Nodes placed over polygon - Paths Strictly in Polygon approach

(c) Nodes placed over polygon - Provide Better Coverage approach

Figure 3.3. Representation of polygon ROI on grid

sub-cells (see also appendix A) are inside the polygon, or not. For the second approach, the same check is performed, however, only for nodes themselves, ignoring the area around them.

3.2.2 Node Placement Optimization

One of the main issues that grid-based methods usually face when used for complex-shaped polygons, is that due to discretization issues the representation of the ROI ends up being a lot different and smaller in comparison with the actual region. That gets translated to incomplete coverage of the ROI. A common practice to overcome this problem is to use a smaller discretization

Figure 3.4. Node placement optimization

scale. However, as mentioned above, the grid size should be proportional to the user-defined d_s . Forcing a d_s that is smaller than the indicated one, in order to provide a descent coverage is a waste of resources, as it increases time, and energy demands for a mission to be carried out. Moreover, large grid dimensions are translated to bigger demands in memory and computational power for the path planning method. In this work, in order to overcome this issue an optimization procedure is proposed, that intends to optimize the nodes' placement, given the user-defined d_s .

The key idea is that by *rotating* and *shifting* the polygon over a grid that respects the defined d_s , more favorable configurations may appear, where the count of nodes that are annotated as *Free Space* is greater. An example where these transformations are applied to a specific ROI is presented in figure 3.4, for the better understanding of this idea. Such configurations are more likely

to provide paths that achieve a high percentage of coverage for the given ROI. Based on this idea, an optimization process utilizing the *Simulated Annealing* [91] algorithm is proceeded, in order to maximize the overall coverage of the ROI. The control variables for the aforementioned optimization problem are selected as follows:

- s_x , which controls the shifting of the polygon over the grid in X axis, in a range $[0, d_n]$,
- s_y , which controls the shifting of the polygon over the grid in Y axis, in a range $[0, d_n]$,
- θ , which controls the rotation of the polygon over the grid, in a range $[0, 90^\circ]$.

It should be noted that the control variables and their ranges are selected so as to provide all the available configurations of node positioning inside the polygon. Combining these three variables in the selected ranges, and allowing values for them in a continuous space, ensures the availability of every possible configuration. For the implementation of the optimization procedure, an augmented grid (figure 3.3(a)) that does not restrict the rotation and shifting for the given polygon, in the given control variables ranges, is constructed.

Optimization Index

The optimization index J intends to represent a quantity directly matched with the coverage potential of a polygon ROI, given a fixed scanning density and is formulated as follows:

$$J = a \cdot J_1 + b \cdot J_2 - c \cdot J_3 \quad (3.7)$$

J consists of three separate, normalized J_i terms, so that:

$$0 \leq J_i \leq 1 \in \mathfrak{R}, i \in \{1, 2, 3\},$$

each aiming to control a specific aspect of the optimal node placement.

J_1 term expresses the fundamental objective of the overall optimization procedure, which is to fit the maximum count of nodes possible inside the given ROI, and is defined as follows:

$$J_1 = \frac{s}{A_p d_n^2}, \quad (3.8)$$

where s stands for the count of nodes placed inside the polygon, that will be used for the MST construction and A_p stands for the area of the polygon.

Denominator represents the theoretical maximum count of nodes that could fit inside the given polygon and is used to normalize J_1 . Thus,

$$s \leq \frac{A_p}{d_n^2}$$

Both A_p and d_n are constant for a specific mission, so, maximizing J_1 term, also maximizes the count of nodes that will be placed inside the polygon.

In addition, J_2 term intends to provide a better placement of the nodes inside the polygon, so as to provide increased coverage for the marginal areas of the ROI, and is defined as follows:

$$J_2 = \frac{A_p}{A_{bb}}, \quad (3.9)$$

where A_{bb} stands for the area of the augmented bounding box. In the example of figure 3.3(a), A_p represents the cyan-colored area of the polygon and A_{bb} represents the area of the green, rectangle bounding box. Since A_p is constant for a specific ROI, by maximizing the overall J_2 term, A_{bb} is minimized. In practice, the addition of this term mostly controls the rotation angle θ , in order to be optimal for the given polygon. Apparently,

$$A_p < A_{bb},$$

thus J_2 term is normalized as well.

Finally, J_3 term aims to improve the placement of the nodes inside the given ROI, attempting to equally align the paths from the ROI's borders and provide increased coverage for the marginal areas as well. J_3 is defined as follows:

$$J_3 = \frac{|\mathbf{x}_{\max_{bb}} - \mathbf{x}_{\max_p}| - |\mathbf{x}_{\min_p} - \mathbf{x}_{\min_{bb}}|}{2 \cdot |\mathbf{x}_{\max_{bb}} - \mathbf{x}_{\min_{bb}}|} + \frac{|\mathbf{y}_{\max_{bb}} - \mathbf{y}_{\max_p}| - |\mathbf{y}_{\min_p} - \mathbf{y}_{\min_{bb}}|}{2 \cdot |\mathbf{y}_{\max_{bb}} - \mathbf{y}_{\min_{bb}}|}, \quad (3.10)$$

where $\{\mathbf{x}_{\max_{bb}}, \mathbf{x}_{\min_{bb}}, \mathbf{y}_{\max_{bb}}, \mathbf{y}_{\min_{bb}}\}$ are the vertices of the augmented bounding box (green box in figure 3.3(a)) and $\{\mathbf{x}_{\max_p}, \mathbf{x}_{\min_p}, \mathbf{y}_{\max_p}, \mathbf{y}_{\min_p}\}$ are the vertices of the standard bounding box (red box in figure 3.3(a)). This term quantifies the absolute difference of margins between the polygon and the augmented bounding box, for each axis. J_3 is normalized as well, with both fractions contributing equally to the overall term. The minimization of J_3 aligns the standard bounding box in the center of the augmented bounding box, and in practice performs micro-adjustments mostly in the s_x and s_y control variables, in order to provide the best possible nodes' placement for the coverage paths.

Finding a tuple of $\{s_x, s_y, \theta\}$ that maximizes J leads to an optimized nodes' setup for the given ROI and d_s . J_1 and J_2 have a positive contribution and act as a reward to the overall optimization index, while J_3 acts as a penalty. The percentage of influence for every term, is regulated by the constants a, b, c . The overall optimization index J is normalized as well, with the constants allowed to take values in the following ranges:

$$0 \leq J < 1 \in \mathfrak{R},$$

$$\text{for } 0 \leq a, b, c \leq 1 \in \mathfrak{R}, \quad a + b = 1$$

The normalization of J helps to make it independent of polygon's size and shape, i.e., no extra effort is needed to adjust the constants a, b, c on each different polygon topology.

Figure 3.5 intends to visually explain the contribution of each of the J_i terms ($i \in [1, 2, 3]$) to the overall optimization procedure, using an example of a fixed ROI and d_s , and showing the effect of the sequential addition of each term. All of these three cases manage to include the same number of nodes in the ROI (54 nodes), thus they are optimal with respect to the J_1 term's objective. The addition of J_2 term (figure 3.5(b)), facilitates the calculation of the optimal for this grid rotation angle θ , affecting also significantly the number of turns in the generated path. Finally, J_3 term's role (figure 3.5(c)) is to center the generated path in the ROI, providing better coverage for the marginal areas. Overall, it should be noted that the simpler the shape of a ROI is, the greater the contribution of J_2 and J_3 terms get. While in complex-shaped, concave ROIs, J_1 term carries the greatest load of this optimization procedure's objective, in simpler cases, such as the one presented in figure 3.5, the role of the other two optimization terms is of critical importance for the achieved coverage, and the overall qualitative features of the paths.

3.2.3 Task Allocation & Path Calculation

Having an optimized representation of the ROI on a grid, DARP algorithm [32] takes over to divide the complete region to sub-regions, exclusive for each UAV, and provide independent paths for all of them utilizing STC [33]. The generated paths have energy efficient characteristics, as they respect UAVs' initial positions, avoiding redundant movements that do not contribute to the coverage process, and reduce the number of unnecessary turns.

DARP - Area Division

DARP algorithm solves the mCPP problem by dividing it into multiple single-agent CPP problems. It is an iterative process implemented to construct an

Figure 3.5. Contribution of each optimization term

assignment matrix, labeling all cells to correspond to a unique UAV. More information regarding DARP's implementation details, along with a complexity analysis, can be found in [32].

After the area division, every UAV undertakes a specific part of the grid to cover. Having exclusive sub-regions ensures the generation of non-intersecting paths, making them safe for multiple UAVs to operate at same time, avoiding potential collisions among them.

Figure 3.6 shows the allocation of an area to four robots, for the initial positions shown, over the execution time of DARP. 3.6(a) shows the initial Voronoi allocation, while 3.6(f) shows the final solution that the algorithm has converged to.

The original version of DARP [32] provides a fair area division, meaning that all UAVs will be assigned with exactly the same percentage of the area to cover. However, in the context of this work, DARP has been extended and is now able to perform a proportional area division as well. The percentages in this case are user-defined, and facilitate the simultaneous operation of heterogeneous UAVs, with different energy and operational capabilities in the same mission. To achieve this, the equation 14 of [32] for the overall cost function, presented below:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{v_n} (k_i - f)^2$$

where k_i and f denote the current portion for the i -th UAV and the global "fair share": $f = \frac{1}{v_n}$ ($\#unoccupied\ cells$ divided by the $\#UAVs$) respectively, is altered as follows:

Figure 3.6. Area allocation during different time-steps of DARP execution
 The ROI is a plain orthogonal area without obstacles and the initial positions of the UAVs are marked with dark blue dots

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{v_n} (k_i - p_i)^2, \quad (3.11)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{v_n} p_i = 1$$

where p_i denotes the target portion for the i -th UAV. Figure 3.7 shows an example of paths' generation for a proportional area allocation based on user-defined percentages.

Figure 3.7. *Proportional area allocation*

Reduced Turns MSTs & Path Generation

Once every robot gets assigned with its exclusive part of the overall area, a single-agent STC problem is solved for every sub-region. For the path generation the standard approach used in the STC algorithm [33] is followed. Specifically, a MST is constructed for every sub-region, and a path that circumnavigates it is generated afterwards. More information about STC algorithm are also included in appendix A.

Due to the spanning-tree nature of the algorithm, it is likely that paths will end up having a lot of unnecessary turns, if no action is taken to avoid them. The number of turns is one of the major factors that affect the flight time and the consumed energy. In order to deal with this problem, the idea is to (i) test a set of n different combinations of weights, to control the connections of nodes in the generated MSTs, for every sub-region, and out of them to (ii) select the setup that generates the MST, which produces the minimum-turns path. In the context of this work, for every sub-region four different combinations are tested, which correspond to the ones that create MSTs connected in the upper, lower, most right, and most left levels available. Figure 3.8 shows an example with the four MSTs on a 3×3 grid for a better understanding.

Figure 3.8. *MSTs connections tested for turn reduction*

Figure 3.9 presents an indicative example of the effect that the turn reduction mechanism has on the overall performance of the system. Without taking care of the path orientation the robot will have to follow a path with 84 turns, as shown in figure 3.9(a), whereas figure 3.9(b) shows that for the same operational environment there is a path that completely covers the ROI with only 42 turns.

(a) ROI coverage with 84 turns

(b) ROI coverage with 42 turns

Figure 3.9. *Turn reduction using the most appropriate MST orientation*

3.3 Simulated Evaluation

This section presents a simulated evaluation of the proposed methodology, that is organized in two separate subsections. Specifically, sub-section 3.3.1 presents an evaluation of the introduced optimization procedure, by analyzing the contribution of each term to the overall quality of the generated paths. In addition to that, a comparison of the proposed method with one of the most powerful, in terms of complete coverage and support of very complex-shaped ROIs, SoA alternative CPP methods [66] is performed. Building on top of that, sub-section 3.3.2 includes a study in order to assess the multi-agent feature of the proposed methodology, comparing the results acquired for two fixed ROIs of different size, when increasing the number of UAVs used for coverage. For reproducibility reasons, all of the ROIs used for the simulated evaluations, along with the extensive list of results produced, are publicly accessible on-line¹.

3.3.1 Single-Agent Paths Evaluation

For the evaluations performed in this sub-section, a set of 20 randomly generated polygon ROIs is used. This set includes convex and concave polygons, with and without obstacles, and a wide range of areas. Both the proposed method and [66] were executed with a fixed scanning density of 40 meters for all ROIs. The simulations were carried out with an also fixed altitude of 40 meters. Moreover, there was made the assumption that the UAV was equipped with an RGB sensor with a HFOV of 73.4° ², in order to perceive the environment. The selected mission parameters, for this sensor, lead to collection of images with a percentage of overlap of 50%, with their neighbor images.

In order to better understand the meaning of overlap, let's imagine two UAVs flying on the same altitude (h), the one next to the other, as shown in figure 3.10. Considering that the two UAVs are equipped with sensors with the same HFOV, the length of the ground covered by each, is:

$$d = 2 \cdot \frac{h \cdot \sin(\text{HFOV}/2)}{\sin(90 - \text{HFOV}/2)} \Rightarrow \quad (3.12)$$

$$d = 2 \cdot h \cdot \tan(\text{HFOV}/2)$$

Now, let's imagine that these two UAVs fly in an altitude and a distance between them, so that the ground covered by each of them, has a part that

¹<https://github.com/savvas-ap/cpp-simulated-evaluations>, accessed on 3 December 2024

²This HFOV was selected as a typical specification for commercial UAVs, based on the sensor that one of the most popular commercial UAVs is equipped with (DJI phantom 4 pro: <https://www.dji.com/phantom-4-pro/info#specs>, accessed on 3 December 2024)

Figure 3.10. Land covered and overlap in the captured images

is also covered by the other one. In this case, it is considered that there is an overlap of information between the collected images. In the context of this chapter, the term *sidelap* refers to the overlapping information between an image with its neighbor, in one of the two sides, while the term *overlap* refers to the overall overlapping information in both sides of the collected image, so that:

$$\text{overlap} = 2 \cdot \text{sidelap} \quad (3.13)$$

In addition, there should be a separation of the terms *overlap* and *percentage of overlap* (p_o). The term *overlap* refers to distance, as explained above, while the term p_o refers to the percentage of overall overlapping information at both sides of an image. The terms d_s , h , p_o , and HFOV can be related with the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} d_s &= d - \text{sidelap} = d - \frac{\text{overlap}}{2} = d - \frac{p_o \cdot d}{2} \Rightarrow \\ d_s &= (2 - p_o) \cdot h \cdot \tan(\text{HFOV}/2) \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

This way, the selected p_o of 50%, for the simulations, corresponds to a 50% of unique information in every collected image, and 25%, at each side, that is included in one of the two neighbor images. It is important to note that p_o should be selected based on the targeted application (e.g., generation of orthomosaics, 3D maps, elevation models etc.).

For evaluation purposes, every ROI is considered to consist of discrete coverage cells, with an area of $0.25 - 4\text{m}^2$, depending on the area of the overall ROI. After the simulation of a generated plan, for each coverage cell is counted the number of scans that was performed during the mission. Based on the number

of scans performed, each cell gets assigned in one of the following categories:

- 0: Not covered
- 1: Covered - unique coverage
- ≥ 2 : Covered - overlapping coverage

Table 4.2 describes all metrics that were used for the performance evaluation of the algorithms, on each different ROI. Out of these metrics, the *PoOC*, the number of *Turns*, and the overall path *Length* are considered to mainly describe the qualitative features of a generated path. In addition to them, there were created a *heatmap of coverage* visualizing the number of visitations at each cell of a ROI, and a *normalized histogram of coverage*, showing the distribution of coverage cells according to the number of visitations performed. To ‘conceptualize the formation of these histograms, consider that for each coverage cell of a ROI, the number of scans performed at it, by multiple passages of the UAV, is counted. After the path simulation, a column is created for every count of performed scans (0, 1, 2, ...), with a height proportional to the number of cells that were visited that many times. To make the scale for the y axis independent of the size of the ROI, the histograms got normalized (the sum of all columns and the maximum possible value for the y axis is always 1). The results out of all ROIs are combined for the overall evaluation of the methods. Specifically, for the metrics presented in table 4.2 are computed averages and, in addition, an aggregate histogram of coverage for every path planning method is created, by the combination of all coverage cells, out of all regions.

Short	Metric	Unit
PoC	Percentage of Coverage (Scans ≥ 1)	%
PoOC	Percentage of Overlapping Coverage (Scans ≥ 2)	%
Turns	Number of Turns/Waypoints	-
N-Turns	Normalized Number of Turns	$\frac{\text{Turns}}{1000\text{m}^2}$
Length	Path Length	km
N-Length	Normalized Path Length	$\frac{\text{m}}{1000\text{m}^2}$

Table 3.1. Evaluation metrics for sub-section 3.3.1

Optimization Terms Importance Analysis

In order to assess the contribution of each optimization term to the quantity of coverage, and the overall quality of paths, an ablation study was performed. The goal was to realize how much, and in which way, the addition of each term affects the ROI coverage task, by studying their effects on the evaluation metrics.

The first 4 columns of table 3.2 and the figures 3.11(a)-3.11(d), present the overall results of this study, as an average out of all ROIs. As the results make clear, the introduction of each term of the optimization procedure, helps to significantly increase the PoC and improve the quality of the generated paths. At this point, it is important to notice that the turn reduction procedure described in section 3.2.3, is applied in all the approaches of STC presented below, independently of the node placement optimization. Comparing the results of the non-optimized STC with those of the proposed approach (J1+J2+J3 terms optimization), the average PoC is increased by 8.64%, the average PoOC gets, in all cases, a value close to the user-defined p_o (50%), the average number of turns is reduced in comparison with the non-optimized STC, while the average length of paths does not get significantly increased, taking into account the benefit in terms of coverage.

Figure 3.12 and table 3.3 present the results for a specific ROI - testbed #1. In testbed #1, the implementation of the original STC algorithm [33] could not run for the selected scanning density, without the proposed optimization scheme. However, the introduction of the proposed optimization procedure managed to find a grid tailored to the ROI's topology, so as to calculate paths, with the defined specifications, that provide decent coverage for the ROI. The first term, J1, is critical for the maximization of the length of paths that will fit in the ROI. At the same time, the other two terms, J2 and J3, are responsible for the optimal placement of paths inside the ROI. As a result, for this mission, that without optimization was considered non-executable, the proposed approach achieves a PoC larger than 94%, and PoOC pretty close to the user-selected p_o (50%).

Average	Non-Optimized STC	J1 Term	J1+J2 Terms	J1+J2+J3 Terms	[66] Length Reduction	[66] Turns Reduction
PoC	87.73%	96.19%	96.02%	96.37%	99.86%	99.91%
PoOC	47.93%	51.96%	51.76%	51.74%	64.85%	71.49%
Turns	85.28	81.83	80.61	82.06	210.39	95.72
N-Turns	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.21	0.11
Length	22.24	24.12	24.12	24.04	33.95	43.15
N-Length	20.81	23.95	23.93	23.90	33.77	40.94

Table 3.2. Average evaluation metrics

Figure 3.11. Aggregate normalized histograms of coverage

Comparison with State-of-the-Art

3.3.1 shows that the proposed optimization procedure significantly improves the effectiveness of the method compared to the non-optimized one, in terms of coverage. The goal of this sub-section is to investigate how the proposed

	Non-Optimized STC	J1 Term	J1+J2 Terms	J1+J2+J3 Terms
PoC	-	89.84%	92.54%	94.19%
PoOC	-	48.72%	48.78%	49.68%
Turns	-	8	8	8
N-Turns	-	0.21	0.21	0.21
Length	-	0.80	0.80	0.80
N-Length	-	21.44	21.44	21.44

Table 3.3. Optimization parameters importance analysis - Testbet #1

	J1+J2+J3 Terms	[66] Length Reduction	[66] Turns Reduction
PoC	95.18%	99.97%	99.05%
PoOC	56.97%	75.41%	81.15%
Turns	84	266	109
N-Turns	0.15	0.48	0.20
Length	13.12	21.68	28.99
N-Length	23.90	39.49	52.79

Table 3.4. Comparison with SoA - Testbed #2

approach stands next to one of the most powerful, in terms of complete coverage, SoA methods. For this reason, coverage plans following the procedure described in [66] are also calculated for all ROIs, with two different objectives (cost functions), one intending to minimize the length of paths, and one intending to minimize the number of turns.

The overall results of this comparison are presented in figures 3.11(d)-3.11(f), and the three last columns of table 3.2. The method proposed in [66] achieved almost complete coverage for all ROIs, with both cost functions, with an average close to 100%. On the other hand, the proposed method achieves a smaller, but still decent PoC (96.37% - i.e., 3.54% smaller than the turn reduction mode, and 3.49% smaller than the length reduction mode of [66]). However, both the number of turns, and the length of produced paths, by the proposed method, are significantly smaller in comparison with both, dedicated to these purposes versions of [66]. To be more precise, the proposed approach achieved a number of average turns 2.56 and 1.16 times smaller than the length reduction, and

Figure 3.12. Optimization terms importance analysis - Testbet #1
 3.12(a)-3.12(g): Heatmaps of coverage, 3.12(b)-3.12(h): Histograms of coverage

turns reduction modes of [66]. In addition, it also achieved an average path's length 1.41 and 1.79 times smaller than the two, aforementioned versions of [66], respectively. This way, the proposed approach combines the advantages of both these dedicated versions, in a more efficient way. Moreover, the PoOC is a lot closer to the user-selected p_o , meaning that there are not performed redundant scans that waste operational resources. Finally, figures 3.11(d)-3.11(f) show that, with the proposed approach, most of the coverage cells are scanned 1 to 2 times, and the maximum number of scans for the same cell is 8, while with [66] most of the coverage cells are scanned 1 to 4 times, and the maximum number of scans for the same cell is 14 (figure 3.11(e)) and 16 (figure 3.11(f)) respectively.

Figure 3.13 and table 3.4 present the results for a specific ROI - testbed #2. [66] manages to achieve an average PoC over 99%, with both cost functions. The average PoC achieved by the proposed method is smaller, but still decent and appropriate for real-world use (over 95%). However, once again, the paths generated by the proposed method are a lot more energy-aware. To be more specific, the number of turns is 3.17 and 1.29 times smaller, and the overall path length is 1.65 and 2.21 times smaller, than the length reduction and the turns reduction modes of [66], respectively. In addition, the count of redundant scans performed with the proposed methodology is significantly smaller as well, managing to keep a percentage of overlapping coverage close to the user-defined p_o (50%).

While the difference in the average PoC between the proposed method and [66] is not negligible, the PoC achieved by the proposed methodology is more than high-enough to face the majority of challenges faced in real-world operations (e.g., [92], [93], [94], [95]). In contrast, it is also worth noting for [66] that in order to achieve almost complete coverage, it forces the vehicles to revisit multiple times specific parts of the ROIs, as shown in figures 3.13(c) and 3.13(e). In addition, both the energy-efficiency features and the multi-UAV capability, that can significantly reduce the operational time, provided by the proposed method, are strong incentives to prefer it in real-world operations.

3.3.2 Multi-Agent Marginal Utility Study

In order to study the effects of using multiple UAVs in coverage missions with the proposed algorithm, a series of simulations was performed. The performed study includes two ROIs with strategically different areas, for a varying number of UAVs, starting from 1 and up to 15. The simulations were carried out with fixed scanning density of 47 meters, altitude of 60 meters, and the same assumption regarding the RGB sensor of all UAVs was made (73.4° HFOV). As a result, the percentage of overlap with the adjacent images was 90%. Finally, the speed for all the UAVs was set to be constant at 3m/s.

Figure 3.13. Comparison with SoA - Testbed #2

3.13(a)-3.13(e): Heatmaps of coverage, 3.13(b)-3.13(f): Histograms of coverage

Table 3.5 shows the metrics that were calculated for the multi-agent study. PoC and PoOC are calculated just as described in subsection 3.3.1. The rest of them are explained below.

In order to calculate the $\#Bat/UAV$ and the *Flight Time (FT)*, *Flight Duration* is calculated first, as follows:

$$\text{FlightDuration} = \frac{\text{Length}}{\text{Speed}} + \text{Turns} \cdot \frac{c_1 \cdot \text{Speed}}{c_2 + |\text{Speed}|} \quad (3.15)$$

The first term corresponds to the time that would be needed in case that the mission was executed with a constant speed, while the second term corresponds to a delay added to this time, for each of the turns in the path. c_1 , c_2 have constant values and they should be chosen accordingly, in order to fine-tune this sigmoid function based on each UAV's type and flight behavior.

The $\#Bat/UAV$ refers to the number of the batteries needed for each UAV in order to complete its path, considering that a single battery can provide 25 minutes of flight duration.

$$\#Bat/UAV = \lceil \frac{\text{FlightDuration}}{25} \rceil, \quad (3.16)$$

where and $\lceil r \rceil$ denotes the ceiling of r (smallest integer that is not smaller than r).

Flight Time refers to the maximum of the *Flight Durations*', for all UAVs participating in a mission. This way:

$$\text{FlightTime} = \text{argmax}[\text{FlightDuration}(v_i)], \quad (3.17)$$

where $i \in [1, v_n]$.

Deployment Time (DT) refers to the indicative time needed to deploy the gear for an experiment (e.g., GCS, UAVs, etc.), from a single human operator.

Short	Metric	Unit
PoC	Percentage of Coverage (Scans ≥ 1)	%
PoOC	Percentage of Overlapping Coverage (Scans ≥ 2)	%
$\#Bat/UAV$	Number of batteries needed for each UAV to complete the mission	-
Flight Time	Theoretical time demanded to complete the mission	min
Deployment Time	Time demanded to deploy the gear	min
Change Battery Delay	Time needed to leave a spot, change battery and continue the mission	min
Total time	Flight Time, including gear deployment and batteries changes	min
Flight Cost	Estimated cost of the flight	Euro

Table 3.5. Evaluation metrics for sub-section 3.3.2

The *Deployment Time* is considered to be 5 minutes, increased by 3 minutes for each of the UAVs participating, and is calculated as follows:

$$\text{DeploymentTime} = 5 + 3 \cdot v_n \quad (3.18)$$

The *Change Battery Delay (CBD)* refers to the time that would be needed if, when a path for a UAV could not be executed with a single battery, the UAV would stop the execution of the mission, fly back to the home position to change battery and return back to the point it stopped the mission to continue. For this delay it is considered that each UAV would need to cross twice an indicative distance, proportional to the area of the ROI, for each battery change that should take place ($\#Bat/UAV > 1$), and that the battery change would also add 3 minutes of delay. Specifically:

$$\text{CBD} = (\#Bat/UAV - 1) \cdot \left(2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\text{area}_{ROI}}}{3 \cdot \text{Speed} \cdot 60} + 3 \cdot v_n \right) \quad (3.19)$$

The *Total Time* comes out from the sum of the *Flight Time*, *Deployment Time*, and *Change Battery Delay*.

$$\text{TotalTime} = FT + DT + CBD \quad (3.20)$$

Finally, the *Flight Cost (FC)* refers to the estimated cost of a flight. Given the KW price of the national power supplier of Greece, the battery capacity, and the flight duration of a common commercial UAV³, the *Flight Cost per Minute (FCM)* is considered to be:

$$\text{FCM} = 0.017228 \text{ Euro/min} \quad (3.21)$$

For the calculation of the *Flight Cost*, *FCM* is multiplied by the *Total Time*, excluding the *Deployment Time* and the time needed to change batteries (however not the time needed to cross the distance in order to change batteries), for each UAV. Specifically:

$$\text{FlightCost} = (\text{TotalTime} - DT - (\#Bat/UAV - 1) \cdot 3) \cdot v_n \cdot \text{FCM} \quad (3.22)$$

It should be noted that the *Flight Cost* calculation does not intend to provide a thorough, or precise economic analysis. The intention of calculating this quantity is to provide an indicative measurable clue, about the productivity gain compared to the increasing operational cost of deploying multiple UAVs. However, one should always have in mind that this operational cost, most of the times is minimal compared to the investment cost that is demanded for

³<https://www.dji.com/phantom-4-pro>, accessed on 3 December 2024

multiple UAVs. For a proper economic analysis to take place, many other factors should be specified, with the most important of them being the field of application. For example, depending on the specific needs of a type of mission, the investment cost for a single UAV, along with the appropriate sensors, could significantly vary (approximately 500-30.000 euros). In addition, there are cases where the significant time reduction will also reduce the demanded human-hours to perform a task (e.g., scan huge agricultural fields), having a great impact on the human-cost, and as a result on the investment's payback time as well. On the contrary, there are cases where the performance gains could not justify the investment cost, such as mapping missions deployed by hobbyists, or even professionals who rarely perform coverage tasks. Finally, there are also cases where the performance gains cannot be directly contradicted to a mission's cost, such as the SAR missions. In this specific application, the increasing number of UAVs does not only reduces the demanded time to scan a ROI and probably detect objects of interest (e.g., injured humans), but also increases the probability of detecting moving targets (e.g., wandering humans in risk) and saving human lives. Overall, this part of the multi-agent study intends to provide a clue about the value of deploying multiple UAVs in coverage missions, however, it cannot be considered in any case as a proper economic analysis.

#UAVs	PoC (%)	PoOC (%)	#Bat/UAV	Flight Time (min)	Deployment Time (min)	Change Battery Delay (min)	Total Time (min)	Flight Cost (Euro)
1	95.28	74.01	1	23.25	8.00	0.00	31.25	0.40
2	95.31	77.01	1	12.70	11.00	0.00	23.70	0.44
3	95.22	81.43	1	8.48	14.00	0.00	22.48	0.44
5	95.76	78.39	1	5.32	20.00	0.00	25.32	0.46
7	95.28	84.96	1	4.28	26.00	0.00	30.28	0.52
9	95.30	84.68	1	3.21	32.00	0.00	35.21	0.50
12	95.62	86.99	1	2.15	41.00	0.00	43.15	0.44
15	95.30	90.52	1	2.15	50.00	0.00	52.15	0.56

Table 3.6. Multi-agent evaluation results - Testbed #3

Green color corresponds to the best run, taking into account all measured metrics

Table 3.6, and figures 3.14 and 3.15 include the results of this multi-agent study for testbed #3. The area of this ROI is 222.720 m², which given the selected mission parameters, is considered to be of a small-average size for coverage missions. From the acquired results, it is clear that increasing the number of UAVs does not significantly affect the achieved PoC. However, it has a slight impact on the PoOC, which has an increasing tendency, when increasing the number of vehicles. In addition, increasing the UAV's number has also a

Figure 3.14. Mission times and flights' cost - Testbed #3

slight impact to the maximum times of revisiting certain points of the ROI, as shown in figure 3.15. The generated mission for a single UAV, in this ROI, was executable with a single battery (Flight Time < 25 min). As expected, the Flight Time constantly decreases when deploying additional vehicles for the coverage mission, however, the Total Time, which also includes the Deployment Time, has a minimum value when performing the mission with 3 UAVs. The addition of the second and the third UAV cause an increase on the Flight Cost by 0.04 Euro, in both cases, compared to the single-UAV deployment. Overall, the Flight Cost for this ROI has a global minimum value when the mission is performed with a single UAV, and an increasing tendency when adding multiple

#UAVs	PoC (%)	PoOC (%)	#Bat/UAV	Flight Time (min)	Deployment Time (min)	Change Battery Delay (min)	Total Time (min)	Flight Cost (Euro)
1	97.66	83.95	8	193.13	8.00	55.92	257.05	3.93
2	97.68	83.57	4	96.50	11.00	32.97	140.47	4.15
3	97.53	85.17	3	65.07	14.00	27.98	107.05	4.50
5	97.67	85.64	2	39.98	20.00	19.99	79.97	4.91
7	97.50	86.44	2	28.46	26.00	25.99	80.45	6.20
9	97.86	88.31	1	22.28	32.00	0.00	54.28	3.45
12	97.68	88.46	1	16.97	41.00	0.00	57.97	3.51
15	97.52	86.64	1	13.78	50.00	0.00	63.78	3.56

Table 3.7. Multi-agent evaluation results - Testbed #4

Green color corresponds to the best run, taking into account all measured metrics

(a) Coverage with 1 UAV

(b) Coverage with 3 UAVs

(c) Coverage with 15 UAVs

Figure 3.15. Heatmaps of coverage - Testbed #3

vehicles (with a local minimum for 12 UAVs). The efficiency gains do not justify the deployment of more than 3 UAVs for this mission, while the Total Time decrease by 8.77 min, could easily justify the Flight Cost increase by 0.04 Euro, for this purpose.

The results of this study for testbed #4 are presented in table 3.7, and figures 3.16 and 3.17. In this case, the area of the ROI is 1.814.063 m², which is considered to be of a large size for coverage missions, given the specific mission parameters. Regarding the PoC, as also noticed from the results for testbed #3, there are no significant discrepancies with respect to the number of UAVs. A slightly increasing tendency in the PoOC was observed, however, smaller than the one observed for testbed #3. The same increase in the maximum times of revisiting certain points of the ROI was observed here as well, as shown in figure 3.17. It is worth noting that in order to perform this mission with a single UAV, 8 batteries are demanded (Flight Time >> 25 min). Overall, the Flight Time decreases constantly, by increasing the number of UAVs. Regarding the Total Time of the mission, it has a global minimum when the mission is performed with 9 UAVs, which is the minimum number of UAVs demanded to perform the mission with a single battery per UAV. The Total Time reduction for the mission performed with 9 UAVs, compared to the one performed with a single UAV, is an impressive amount of 202.77 min. The even more impressive fact, is that the estimated Flight Cost has a steep increasing tendency till the point that the mission is not executable with a single battery per UAV (7 UAVs), and a global minimum value right after it, for the mission performed with 9 UAVs. From that point on, both the Total Time, and the Flight Cost slightly increase, however the estimated values suggest that performing the mission with more UAVs, is still far more efficient than performing it with less than 9. Overall, for such a big ROI it is clear that it is not efficient, by any means, to deploy a mission with less vehicles than the number demanded to perform it with a single battery per vehicle. In addition, it is worth noting that with most of the available tools that do not support multi-agent operations, this mission could not be executed at all, as they do not also support to pause and continue the mission from a certain point.

As a general conclusion of this multi-agent study, the deployment of multiple unmanned vehicles in coverage tasks can introduce huge efficiency benefits under specific conditions. When the objective of such missions is to scan very large areas, or in cases where the missions' duration is critical, such as in the SAR domain, the multi-agent feature can not only introduce tremendous benefits, regarding both the missions' duration and operational cost, but can also unlock a whole new range of possible applications. However, as in most cases, here as well, there is a marginal utility point where the addition of any further vehicle does not only stops offering benefits, but on the contrary increases cost and

Figure 3.16. Mission times and flights' cost - Testbed #4

decreases the mission's efficiency. A good starting point when considering the number of UAVs that should participate in a mission, is the count of vehicles that makes possible the execution of a mission with a single battery per vehicle, something that is advisable if the application justifies this extra investment cost.

Algorithm's Execution Time

For all of the executions of the proposed, optimized mCPP algorithm in the context of this multi-agent study, the needed computation time was logged and included in tables 3.8 and 3.9. As an overall comment, for both testbeds the optimization procedure consumes the greatest amount of the execution time. In addition, the time demanded to run the optimization procedure for all cases of each testbed is approximately the same, as this task is dependent only on the generated grid's dimensions, and not on the number of vehicles. In general, the optimization procedure inherits the same complexity with simulated annealing algorithm [96]. In addition, more specific information about the run time of the path planning and the area allocation procedures, as well as a thorough computational and memory complexity analysis of DARP algorithm can be found in the original paper [32].

3.4 Real Life Experiments

In this section are presented some indicative examples of real-world applications, where the end-to-end platform presented in appendix B -using the mCPP

methodology presented and evaluated in this section- can be used to obtain

(a) Coverage with 1 UAV

(b) Coverage with 9 UAVs

(c) Coverage with 15 UAVs

Figure 3.17. Heatmaps of coverage - Testbed #4

#UAVs	Optimization Time	Overall Execution Time
	(sec)	(sec)
1	2.87	2.88
2	2.69	2.69
3	2.74	2.75
5	2.73	2.73
7	2.78	2.78
9	2.77	2.77
12	2.95	2.96
15	2.75	2.75
Average	2.79	2.79

Table 3.8. Execution times - Testbed #3

#UAVs	Optimization Time	Overall Execution Time
	(sec)	(sec)
1	16.47	16.49
2	16.70	16.72
3	16.17	16.19
5	16.30	16.34
7	16.35	16.42
9	16.02	16.08
12	15.91	16.34
15	16.30	16.70
Average	16.28	16.41

Table 3.9. Execution times - Testbed #4

data, along with results that are usually desired in such tasks. This way, the functionalities and efficiency of the platform are evaluated through the quality of the acquired data, and the produced results, i.e., through the reason why such platforms are developed and used. To acquire the desired photogrammetry

results, the gathered data were processed with the use of the web platform of OpenDroneMap, WebODM⁴. WebODM is a powerful, open-source solution for processing UAV imagery, and acquiring results in a wide range of applications. The objective of this section is to present the applicability, and the robust operation of the proposed platform, in real-world coverage missions.

A quantity that needs to be explained for the explanation of the results is Ground Sampling Distance (GSD), that is calculated using equation 3.12, and the resolution of the sensor that will be used⁵, a value that is retrieved from the database of the platform:

$$\text{GSD} = \frac{d}{\text{res}_h} = \frac{2 \cdot h \cdot \tan(\text{HFOV}/2)}{\text{res}_h}, \quad (3.23)$$

where res_h is the resolution of the horizontal dimension of the sensor.

3.4.1 Experimental Setup

For the real-world experiments were used:

- a common commercial laptop⁶, as a portable GCS,
- a swarm of common commercial UAVs⁷,
- a set of android smartphone devices⁸, to run the custom-developed application, described in section B.3, and
- a portable 4G router⁹, as an intermediate communication layer between the smartphones and the portable GCS.

The hardware setup used, is shown in figure 3.18.

3.4.2 Precision Agriculture Application

As reported in [98] remote sensing from unmanned aircraft systems is a very important new technology that introduced many benefits for the farmers in the field of precision agriculture, especially crop nutrient management. According

⁴<https://www.opendronemap.org/webodm/>, accessed on 3 December 2024

⁵GSD is calculated for the take off position, and is constant considering that the whole ROI is flat and has almost the same elevation. In order to have a constant GSD for ROIs with altitude variations, the flight altitude should be adjusted based on the actual distance from the ground, at each point of the region (see also [97]).

⁶Dell XPS 9570

⁷<https://www.dji.com/phantom-4-pro>, accessed on 3 December 2024

⁸Xiaomi Mi Max 2

⁹tp-link M7350

Figure 3.18. *Experimental hardware setup*

to [99], some of the advances that the use of UAVs introduced in agriculture are (i) the affordable crop mapping, (ii) the early identification of problems through vegetation indices, that prevents yield losses, and (iii) the better planning of crop management operations.

In order to prove the efficiency of the developed platform in the collection of data for such tasks, an experiment was performed in a field with olive trees. The main objectives of this experiment were to (i) get an updated image of the field on map, in order to facilitate the planning of various works, (ii) acquire some kind of plant health information, that could give indications on the year's harvest and possible actions that should be taken to improve it, and (iii) acquire some kind of bio-mass estimation that is in general useful to monitor plant and weeds growth, as well as organize a wide range of agricultural tasks.

Depending on the type of operations, and the accuracy of data required, UAVs used in precision agriculture are usually equipped with RGB, multi-spectral, or hyper-spectral cameras. In this experiment participated two UAVs, equipped with RGB cameras. The mission altitude was selected to be 18 meters, and the percentage of overlap (p_o) 90%, as advised from the WebODM documentation for a decent 3D reconstruction. The selected altitude and p_o resulted in a d_s of about 14 meters, and the GSD in the collected images gets a value of 0.49 cm/px. In addition, the operational speed was selected to be 2 m/s, which is low enough to not spoil the quality of the collected images, and the gimbal pitch was selected to be 45 degrees, an angle that usually contributes in the quality of an area's 3D reconstruction. Overall, for this ROI were collected 525 images, that were later used for the reconstruction of the results presented below.

(a) Orthomosaic overlaid by the ROI and generated paths

(b) Plant health

(c) Point cloud

(d) Elevation model

Figure 3.19. *Photogrammetry results for precision agriculture*

Figure 3.19 illustrates the key outcomes of this experiment, which are usually desired in this type of precision agriculture applications. It is important to note here that all results depicted in figure 3.19 were created from the data gathered in a single run, with the mission parameters described above.

Figure 3.19(a) shows the area that was actually covered, along with the polygon ROI and the calculated paths. It is clear from the result that almost the whole user-defined ROI was successfully covered, and that the data gathered were sufficient for a qualitative representation of the desired area. This 2D reconstruction of the ROI is called orthomosaic, and it was created to satisfy the objective (i) of this experiment. Orthomosaics are high-resolution maps created by aerial images, geometrically corrected (“orthorectified”) such that the scale is uniform. Orthomosaics can be used for an overall monitoring of the ROI, as the information on the existing map gets updated, and for making useful measurement (e.g., planting lines and distances, percentage of ground covered

by vegetation etc.). In 3.19(b) the created orthomosaic is used to produce a plant health map, to satisfy the objective (ii) of the experiment. Such maps, are specifically targeted towards agriculture. Their main purpose is to allow an exploration of the agricultural data even more deeply. Once the relevant plant health ranges have been identified, the color map provides a thresholding tool, able to quantify damage and predict yields by showing the areas within specific ranges. Finally, 3.19(c) and 3.19(d) show a pointcloud and an elevation map of the ROI, respectively, that were created to satisfy the objective (iii) of the experiment. Pointclouds are created by the combination of visual and depth information in order to produce a 3D representation of the scenery. On the other hand, elevation maps use only depth information, in order to create a color map that visualizes the altitude differences in a ROI. Both of them are useful for the biomass estimation, and a more efficient planning of tasks in the agricultural fields.

Overall, the results created for the scanned ROI are satisfactory and correspond to the actual condition and topology of the field. The user-defined ROI is covered almost completely and the gathered data are sufficient to produce a qualitative representation of the field, proving that the developed platform is appropriate for such operations. Finally, the ability to use multiple UAVs, allows (i) the faster conduction of tasks, and (ii) the coverage of large areas within a single mission, something that is not always possible with a single UAV. For the mission presented here, the execution time was 7.56 minutes, while the estimated time to execute the same mission, with a single UAV, is about 14.6 minutes.

3.4.3 Search and Rescue Application

According to [100], the introduction of UAVs in SAR operations, has managed to face one of the very significant problems in this kind of missions. Specifically, the resources and time that were required to deploy rescue teams before, were major bottleneck that decreased the victim's chance of survival. Thanks to the advances in the field of UAVs, now the assessment of the situation, or the damage caused by natural or man-made disasters, and the location of victims in the debris, can be done with these small, unmanned vehicles, reducing both the deployment time, and the operational risk to the the minimum. As reported in [101], UAVs also offer increased precision and the capability of long duration missions, that are both critical in some cases. In addition, both equipment, and operational costs are significantly reduced, making aerial SAR missions more affordable and available to a wider range incidents.

For the evaluation of the proposed platform in this kind of operations, was performed a mission with the following imaginary scenario: In a complex

of business buildings, on a public holiday, there was an information about a suspicious meeting for smuggling, where a blue or a silver vehicle could be involved. A team of first responders deployed a swarm of UAVs in the region with the objective to completely cover the ROI, and detect any possible vehicle in the area, that fits the available description. The images delivered in the GCS, in real-time, were fed to an object detection algorithm (YOLO v3 [102]) in order to detect the vehicles of interest, during the execution of the mission, and locate them on map. Finally, an orthomosaic was created with the collected photographs to update the image on map, and provide better overall situational awareness.

For this mission, in an attempt to minimize the time from deployment, to the detection of vehicle(s) of interest, all of the available UAVs were utilized. This way, the mission was performed with 3 UAVs, however, due to the lower battery level on one of them, the tasks were allocated proportionally, with this UAV undertaking only the 15% of the overall region, and the other two undertaking 40% and 45% respectively. In addition, due to the direct visual contact, the area around the point of deployment was excluded from the ROI. The mission altitude was selected to be 50 meters, in order to fly over the buildings in the field, and the p_o 160%, so as to cover all points multiple times and reduce the risk of losing the detection of possible targets, because of their movement. The selected altitude and p_o resulted in a d_s of about 28.5 meters, and the GSD in the collected images gets a value of 1.36cm/px. As in the previous experiment, the operational speed was selected to be 2 m/s, and the gimbal pitch 45 degrees, to ease the detection of the vehicles from the object detection algorithm [102]. From this mission were collected 432 images in total, that were used for the acquirement results presented below.

Figure 3.20(a) shows the defined ROI and the mission generated with these specifications, along with the area that was actually covered and the location of the detected objects of interest. As in the previous experiment, the whole ROI was successfully covered, and the gathered data are sufficient for a qualitative representation of the area. Figure 3.20(b) shows the output of the detection algorithm for the vehicles of interest (zoomed image).

Regarding the execution time, this mission needed 8.7 minutes to be completed, while for a single-UAV mission with the same specifications the estimated time for completion is more than 21. The utilization of multiple UAVs, also increased the probability to detect the objects of interest earlier. Indeed, the time needed from the beginning of the mission to the detection of the vehicles was just about 3.5 minutes.

Overall, the features and functionalities of the proposed mCPP approach and the end-to-end platform, seemed to be extremely useful in real-world operational conditions. The results achieved in both cases, presented in this section, were

(a) Area covered and location of detected objects

(b) Cars of interest detected in the mission's ROI

Figure 3.20. SAR coverage mission

very satisfactory for this type of operations. In addition, the multi-agent capability, and the energy efficiency features provided, are strong incentives to

prefer the proposed solution over other mission planners, commercial or not, that are currently available.

3.5 Conclusion

This paper aims at bridging the gap between the already existing, powerful UAVs platforms and the effective utilization of multiple UAVs, in the coverage path planning domain. Towards that purpose, first, the original grid-based STC algorithm [33] was revisited to enable the grid's adjustment on the specific geometrical characteristics of the region of interest. To achieve that, an optimization approach, based on Simulated Annealing algorithm [91], was put in charge of the discretization strategy that ultimately controls the coverage performance. The efficiency of the optimization scheme is validated through an extensive series of simulations, in comparison with a SoA CPP alternative methodology [66]. Then, DARP algorithm [32] takes over to divide the previously optimized grid into as-many-as-the-number-of-UAVs exclusive areas, with respect to their operational capabilities.

The realization of the aforescribed methodology is achieved through a production-ready software platform, that respects all the modern-software best practices. Two field experiments with different objectives were performed to prove the robustness of the platform: (i) a precision agriculture application, and (ii) a SAR mission. In both real-world demonstrations, the proposed platform preserved all the desired features of the commercial UAVs platforms, while at the same time, it achieved tremendous mission-duration improvements, that were directly proportional to the number of UAVs deployed in each mission. Such a feature is of paramount importance, as it enables the seamless utilization of more UAVs to trade-off their battery limitations, which is the one of the major factors that, at the moment, constrains the deployment of UAVs in specific types of missions.

4

Systematically Improving the Real-World Efficiency of Grid-Based CPP Methodologies

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4.1 Introduction

The work presented in this chapter focuses on grid-based path planning methods, i.e., methods that use a grid (matrix) to design the output trajectories. The main objective of this work is to completely overcome the issues inherited by the grid-based nature of the mCPP algorithm presented in the previous chapter, to provide a solution with increased efficiency and effectiveness in real-world

operations. This way, the pipeline presented in section 3.2 serves as a basis, and gets extended to improve the core method, and resolve any remaining issues. The discretization issues accompanying grid-based methods are explained and discussed, proposing ideas and solutions to overcome them. While this work is built around the mCPP method presented in chapter 3, the whole concept can be modified, and applied to different grid-based solutions to overcome similar issues as well. This chapter serves as a guide for increasing the efficiency of such methods in real-world operations, while at the same time a very powerful CPP solution for UAVs' RS operations, with ad-hoc coverage modes to serve different needs and objectives, is introduced.

4.1.1 Contributions

The work presented in this chapter takes advantage of the coordinates' transformation, and the optimization procedure presented in chapter 3, and introduces three different methods to represent the ROI on grid, and generate STC trajectories, resulting in three CPP modes with features that make them more appropriate for specific operations. Specifically:

- **Geo-fenced Coverage Mode (GCM)** which guarantees no crossing of the paths with the NGZs, or the boundaries of the ROI.
- **Better Coverage Mode (BCM)** which guarantees no crossing of the paths with the NGZs, but allows the paths to get slightly outside the ROI to provide better coverage in the marginal areas.
- **Complete Coverage Mode (CCM)** which guarantees no crossing of the paths with the NGZs, or the boundaries of the ROI, but also ensures complete coverage even for the most complex-shaped regions, by modifying the principals of STC algorithm.

The result is a CPP method which can face a wide range of challenging real-world operations, appropriate for use with any (commercial or custom) UAV capable of following pre-defined trajectories, and highly efficient in RS operations, since it ensures data collection with the demanded overlaps for various applications.

The efficiency and robustness of the core method in real-world operations have been proven through simulated evaluations, and on-the-field demonstrations. The new path planning modes introduced in this work are thoroughly evaluated using the same publicly available methodology and benchmark ROIs, to provide a direct comparison with the SoA CPP alternative.

The three major contributions of this work are:

- The presented ideas and introduced methods for the representation of the ROI on grid, which manage to address the issues usually faced in real-world operations with grid-based CPP methods.
- A highly efficient in UAVs' real-world operations CPP method, with the three aforementioned ad-hoc coverage modes.
- A quantitative simulated evaluation performed using publicly available ROIs, method, and metrics, which proves the CPP solution's claimed benefits, and sets a new benchmark for CPP methods in general (grid-based or not).

4.1.2 Chapter Outline

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows: section 4.2 explains the parameters that should be considered in coverage missions with UAVs, and the peculiarities met in grid-based methods that deal with this problem, section 4.3 introduces the three novel path planning modes developed in the context of this work, explaining them both from a technical, and a functional perspective, section 4.4 presents the simulated evaluation performed for the newly introduced modes, and finally, section 4.5 summarizes the presented work.

4.2 Problem Formulation

4.2.1 CPP for UAVs' RS Operations

The CPP problem for UAVs' RS operations lies in the calculation of trajectories which can provide complete coverage for the selected ROI, respecting all the hardware, legal and user-defined specifications, and limitations. Many approaches try to provide that by simultaneously minimizing the demanded time and energy to perform a specific mission. With the objective to collect data out of the whole region, one or more UAV(s) are utilized, each of them carrying a sensor with certain specifications (e.g., horizontal and vertical resolution (res_h , res_v) and field of view (HFOV, VFOV, usually provided by the sensors' manufacturers in degrees)). The post-processing data analysis required for a specific application (e.g., generation of orthomosaics, elevation models, 3D representations, etc.) indicates the desired overlap between two sequential image captures (sidelap and frontlap), usually defined in percentages (percentage of sidelap p_s and percentage of frontlap p_f).

The area of land covered in a single image capture from the UAV, at an altitude h , is $d_h \cdot d_v$, where:

$$d_h = 2 \frac{h \sin(\text{HFOV}/2)}{\sin(90 - \text{HFOV}/2)} \Rightarrow d_h = 2 h \tan(\text{HFOV}/2) \quad (4.1)$$

$$d_v = 2 \frac{h \sin(\text{VFOV}/2)}{\sin(90 - \text{VFOV}/2)} \Rightarrow d_v = 2 h \tan(\text{VFOV}/2) \quad (4.2)$$

Having calculated d_h and d_v , a quantity that is of great importance for RS applications is the Ground Sampling Distance (GSD), that corresponds to the length of land captured in each pixel (usually counted in cm/pixel for UAV missions):

$$\text{GSD} = \min \left(\frac{d_h}{\text{res}_h}, \frac{d_v}{\text{res}_v} \right) \quad (4.3)$$

The altitude along with the desired sidelap defines the distance that two sequential coverage trajectories should have, a quantity that in this work will be referred as scanning density (d_s) from now on:

$$d_s = d_h - \text{sidelap} = d_h - p_s d_h = (1 - p_s) d_h \quad (4.4)$$

Finally, the desired frontlap indicates the specific capturing positions, or along with the UAV's speed, the capturing frequency. From now on, in this work, we will refer to the distance between two sequential capturing positions as capturing density (d_c):

$$d_c = d_v - \text{frontlap} = d_v - p_f d_v = (1 - p_f) d_v \quad (4.5)$$

Figure 4.1 visually summarizes the parameters met in UAVs' RS operations, where C_i corresponds to the UAVs' capturing positions. In this figure, the variables that refer to the longer side of the sensor are mentioned as horizontal (HFOV, d_h), while the ones that refer to the shorter side of sensor are mentioned as vertical (VFOV, d_v).

4.2.2 Representation of the ROI on Grid

As mentioned above, a family of methods utilizes a grid for the calculation of the coverage trajectories, to provide a solution to the CPP problem. In this case, everything mentioned in section 4.2.1 is still valid, however, there is one additional step that should be performed before calculating the trajectories. The ROI in such coverage operations is usually a user-defined polygon, formatted in WGS84 coordinates [90], using latitude (lat) and longitude (lon) to describe its vertices, that depending on the method may also include NGZs inside it:

$$\text{ROI} = \{(\text{lat}_1, \text{lon}_1), \dots, (\text{lat}_n, \text{lon}_n)\} \quad (4.6)$$

Figure 4.1. Summary of UAVs' RS operations—parameters explained.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{NGZs} = & \{ \{ (\text{lat}_{\text{NGZ}_1|1}, \text{lon}_{\text{NGZ}_1|1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{\text{NGZ}_1|n_1}, \text{lon}_{\text{NGZ}_1|n_1}) \}, \\ & \dots, \{ (\text{lat}_{\text{NGZ}_m|1}, \text{lon}_{\text{NGZ}_m|1}), \dots, (\text{lat}_{\text{NGZ}_m|n_m}, \text{lon}_{\text{NGZ}_m|n_m}) \} \} \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

where n is the count of polygon vertices, NGZ_i ($i = 0, \dots, m$) stands for the NGZ's number (pointer), n_i ($i = 0, \dots, m$) is the count of vertices for each NGZ, and m the count of NGZs. For a grid-based method to deal with such ROIs, each ROI should be first represented on the respective grid. However, this task is not always trivial, and can significantly affect the performance of the overall method for the CPP problem. That is because the ROI is a continuous polygon shape, and its representation on a grid corresponds to a discretization procedure that -by nature- introduces an error, meaning that the original ROI and its representation on the grid cannot be identical. Given the fact that the discretization scale (i.e., the size of the grids' cells), in most cases, cannot be small enough to minimize this error (since it is dependent on the specifications of each respective CPP methodology), the discretization error can be high enough to hinder the application of such methods to real-world problems.

For the efficient application of grid-based methods on real-world problems, two different factors should be considered during the representation of the ROI on a grid (taking as granted that the ROI itself, and the discretization scale cannot be changed): (i) the criterion(-a) that will be used to characterize each cell of the grid (obstacle/free space), and (ii) the relative placement between the ROI and the grid. From now on, when we refer to the actual region we will use the terms *ROI* and *NGZs*, and when we refer to the representation on grid, we will use the terms *free space* and *obstacle*.

Regarding the first factor, the simplest way to decide whether a cell of the grid belongs to the ROI is to check if its center is placed inside the ROI. A different approach is to determine based on the percentage of the cells' area that belongs to the ROI (i.e., if the cell's area inside the ROI $> 50\%$, then the cell belongs to the ROI). However, in both cases, the discretization procedure does not consider the specificities of the respective path-planning approach that will be applied as the next step. To explain why this can be an issue, figure 4.2 shows an example of a ROI's representation on grid, having as a criterion the placement of the cells' centers. From this figure, it is clear that (i) the representation of the ROI on the grid is not identical to the ROI itself, and (ii) depending on the CPP method that will be used, it is likely that one of the following will happen:

Figure 4.2. Discretization procedure - representation of the ROI on grid.

- There will not be achieved complete coverage of the ROI, as parts of it are considered “obstacles”.
- Coverage paths can be generated outside the actual ROI since there are parts outside of it that are represented as ROI.
- Coverage paths can be generated so that they will cross the user-defined NGZs, for the same reason.

While the above points may not always be that important, depending on the type of application, they could have a very negative impact (i.e., if an NGZ contains an obstacle that the UAV can crash, the generated trajectories should never cross them).

Moreover, the second factor mentioned above -as identified in chapter 3- can significantly impact the discretization error produced from the representation procedure, directly related to the coverage results that will be achieved during the mission. As a reminder, it was identified that the relative placement between the grid and the ROI could lead to many different states that can be more or less favorable for the coverage of the ROI during real-world missions. Figure 4.3 shows an example of the same ROI represented on two different grids, where in figure 4.3(a) the grid that has not been transformed (25 nodes can be used for trajectories' generation), and in figure 4.3(b) the grid has been rotated and shifted over two axes (30 nodes can be used for trajectories' generation). In this example, it is clear that for the rotated and shifted grid, the relative placement between it and the ROI is more favorable for the coverage procedure since, not only the area that is considered to belong to the ROI is larger (5 additional nodes), but also, the representation is a lot closer to the actual shape of the region. Based on this idea, the "Node Placement Optimization" procedure was introduced and evaluated extensively.

For the representation of the ROI on grid in the previous chapter, the check of whether all four STC sub-nodes' centers are placed inside the ROI or not, is used as a criterion for the characterization of each cell as *obstacle*, or *free space* (in case you have not done it yet, the understanding of STC algorithm included in appendix A will be very useful for the understanding of certain aspects of this work as well). If all sub-nodes' centers are placed inside the ROI, then the cell will be labeled as *free space* and will participate in the coverage trajectories generation procedure without any limitations. This way, some of the specificities of the STC algorithm are incorporated into the ROI representation procedure; however, the provided solution is not flawless, as there are few cases where the generated paths can cross the user-defined NGZs or the margins of the ROI. A specific example ROI (testbed 1), carefully selected to highlight the problems that this approach can cause in certain cases, is presented in section 4.3.2. In this ROI are generated coverage trajectories with the core method, and all three coverage modes introduced in this chapter, to demonstrate how each of them deals with such cases.

4.3 Methodology

This section presents the newly introduced coverage method, with three ad-hoc coverage modes, each tailored to serve different missions with specific requirements. Following the pipeline presented in chapter 3, this method receives as input a user-defined ROI formatted in WGS84 coordinates and the mission's specifications, and produces as output coverage trajectories that

(a) Representation on a non-transformed grid

(b) Representation on rotated and shifted grid

Figure 4.3. Representation of the ROI on two different grids

are directly executable by any type of UAV, able to follow a pre-defined path formatted in WGS84 coordinates. Furthermore, building upon the standard CPP problem, this work addresses challenges such as strictly geo-fenced coverage of a ROI, generating paths without sharp turns or intersecting trajectories and guaranteeing complete coverage for any possible shape of ROI.

Since it is not feasible to provide a single solution that combines all the aforementioned benefits, the separate coverage modes are introduced, each with a unique combination of features that make it more suitable for specific types of operations. The following coverage modes are extensively described in this section: (i) **Geo-fenced Coverage Mode (GCM)**, (ii) **Better Coverage Mode (BCM)**, and (iii) **Complete Coverage Mode (CCM)**. All three modes ensure that the generated trajectories do not pass through any NGZ,

and the special features of each coverage mode are presented in detail in table 4.1. These coverage modes represent significant advancements in grid-based CPP methods and provide solutions to the remaining limitations associated with them.

Features	GCM	BCM	CCM
Geo-fenced Trajectories	✓	✗	✓
90° Turns	✓	✓	✗
Non-Overlapping Trajectories	✓	✓	✗
Complete Coverage	✗	✗	✓

Table 4.1. *Features of the separate coverage modes.*

Figure 4.4 presents the flowchart of the overall CPP method. The left part of the figure refers to the components that are common with the ones presented in chapter 3, including the input parameters, the coordinates' transformation, and the optimization procedure that calculates the optimal grid for each specific ROI. The right part of the figure refers to the ad-hoc coverage modes, introduced in this work, including the specific checks that are performed for the ROI's representation on grid (the numbers refer to the sections that describe these checks), and the trajectory generation procedure.

In order to arrive at the three distinct coverage modes, this work introduces novel approaches for labeling the grid's cells, taking into consideration the application of STC in the next step. Additionally, information acquired during the labeling stage is utilized during the path-generation process to ensure compliance with each mode's specific features.

To better organize the presented methodology, section 4.3.1 outlines the various checks performed while labeling nodes. Section 4.3.2 then describes the three coverage modes, with references made to the previous sub-section as necessary.

The careful consideration given to the labeling of nodes and its incorporation into the path generation process is a significant contribution to the field of grid-based CPP methods. This work offers a detailed and organized presentation of its methodology, making it more accessible to researchers, and practitioners alike. Further research can continue to build upon and expand the presented coverage modes.

Figure 4.4. Flowchart of the introduced CPP method with three ad-hoc coverage modes. *Core Method refers to the methodology presented in chapter 3

4.3.1 Grid's Cells Labeling Methods

To perform the representation of the ROI on grid, as a first step, it is checked which of the grid's cells belong to the ROI. As a next step, for each cell belonging to the ROI, it is checked if it also belongs to an NGZ; thus, should be excluded from the ROI. Section 4.3.1 presents the two different checks that can be performed for the polygon, and section 4.3.1 presents the other two that can be performed for the NGZs afterward.

3.1.1 Polygon

(1) Sub-nodes checking method

This is the simpler of the two checks. According to this one, if at least one of the four STC sub-cells' centers (figure 4.5(a)) is placed inside the polygon of the ROI, the respective mega-cell is labeled as *free space* and will be used for path generation. To label a mega-cell as *obstacle*, all of the four sub-cells' centers should be outside of the ROIs' polygon. Figure 4.6 shows an example of such checks to provide a better understanding.

(2) Cross checking method

This check includes three separate steps. Specifically:

- **Step 1:** the first check performed is whether the center of each mega-cell of the grid (figure 4.5(a)) is placed inside the polygon of the ROI. The ones that are placed outside of the ROI are labeled at this step as *obstacle*.
- **Step 2:** for the remaining mega-cells (that are not labeled as *obstacle* in the previous step), it is checked if the rectangle whose vertices are the centers of the four sub-cells (figure 4.5(b)) is intersected by the polygon of the ROI. If an intersection is detected, then the mega-cell is labeled as an *obstacle*.

- **Step 3:** for the remaining mega-cells, a final additional check is performed. For each mega-cell a cross-shaped polygon is created, such as the one shown in figure 4.5(c). This polygon has strictly 90° angles, the vertices inside the mega-cell are the sub-cells' centers, and the "external" sides of it are part of the sides of the mega-cell. The sides of the cross-shaped polygon are classified into four groups, specifically:

- Group A: sides (1), (2), (3)
- Group B: sides (4), (5), (6)
- Group C: sides (7), (8), (9)
- Group D: sides (10), (11), (12)

Separately for each group, it is checked whether there is an intersection between the polygon of the ROI and the sides of each group. If an intersection is detected for all four groups, the mega-cell is labeled as *obstacle* because there is no way to generate a path inside this cell that will not cross the boundaries of the ROI. However, if there is no intersection, the mega-cell is labeled as *free space* and can be used for path generation. To prevent path generation that intersects the polygon, the cost for connecting the nodes in the graph is changed to an extremely high value for directions where an intersection with the ROI's polygon would occur. This ensures that there will not be a connection in the MST with the respective neighbor node, preventing the generation of a path in that direction. An example of grid representation using this method is shown in figure 4.7.

3.1.2 No-Go-Zones

(1) Sub-nodes checking method

Figure 4.5. *Mega-cell and sub-cells: Checks performed*

Figure 4.6. Representation of the ROI on the grid with the sub-nodes checking method.

Figure 4.7. Representation of the ROI on the grid with the cross-checking method.

This check has the same rationale as section 3.1.1-(1), however, this time it is performed for the NGZs instead of the ROI. To exclude a mega-cell from the ROI (label it as *obstacle*), according to this criterion, all of the sub-cells' centers should be placed inside an NGZ. Otherwise, it is still considered to be

Figure 4.10. Example of coverage paths with BCM in testbed #1.

Complete Coverage Mode (CCM)

CCM has the main objective of providing complete coverage while being strictly geo-fenced, no matter how complex the ROI may be. An example of the coverage path generated by CCM, in testbed #1, is shown in figure 4.11. For the representation of the ROI on the grid in this mode sections 3.1.1-(1) and 3.1.2-(1) checks are used. This way, the STC path is generated during the next step both outside of the margins of the region and inside the NGZs. To fix this issue, the next post-processing step is applied. Specifically, the points where the generated trajectory intersects the ROI or an NGZ are detected, and the path placed outside the ROI, or inside an NGZ is “cropped” on the boundaries of the respective polygon. This way, it is ensured that the generated path will be strictly geo-fenced. To achieve that, however, several STC principles are violated. Specifically, the generated trajectory does not have a constant d_s in the whole ROI, it includes turns that are not 90° , and it can have intersecting points and backtracking. This coverage mode is ideal for cases where complete coverage of a ROI in a strictly geo-fenced environment is critical, and the vehicle(s) utilized in the mission can handle sharp turns. The trajectories generated by this mode have a significantly increased number of turns compared to the other two, as additional turns are added for every “path cropping”. In addition to that, it has a slightly increased path length. This way, CCM, in order to provide complete coverage, can be slightly less efficient in terms of time and energy.

Figure 4.11. Example of coverage paths with CCM in testbed #1.

4.4 Evaluation

4.4.1 Evaluation Methodology

To provide a direct comparison with alternative SoA CPP approaches, the same methodology and benchmark ROIs¹ used in the previous chapter, were used for the evaluation study of the newly introduced modes as well. An additional metric, referring to the estimated mission execution time, given a speed of 3 m/s and a fixed delay of 1sec per turn was added. Table 4.2 summarizes the evaluation metrics. In addition to them, for each ROI the *heatmap of coverage* introduced in the previous chapter was generated as well, visualizing the number of visitations performed at each coverage cell. Finally, out of the average results a radar chart was generated to provide a qualitative presentation of the modes at a glance. For the five non-normalized metrics, each mode is ranked in a scale of [1,5], where 1 corresponds to the worst value among them (not necessarily the smallest), and 5 to the best one (not necessarily the largest). This chart helps to better understand where each coverage mode outmatches the others and what is sacrificed to achieve that. Out of them, *PoC* is better when the value is higher, *Turns*, *Length*, and *Time* are better when the value is smaller, and *PoOC* is better when it is closer to the user-defined 50% (2 p_s).

4.4.2 Modes Evaluation

Table 4.3 presents the average metrics out of the simulated evaluation in the 20 benchmark ROIs, for all modes. From these results, it becomes clear that GCM manages to achieve almost identical scores with the core method presented in chapter 3, while fixing the issue of the generated trajectories crossing the

¹<https://github.com/savvas-ap/cpp-simulated-evaluations>, accessed on 3 December 2024

Short	Metric	Unit
<i>PoC</i>	Percentage of Coverage (Scans ≥ 1)	%
<i>PoOC</i>	Percentage of Overlapping Coverage (Scans ≥ 2)	%
<i>Turns</i>	Number of Turns/Waypoints	-
<i>N-Turns</i>	Normalized Number of Turns	$\frac{\text{Turns}}{1000 \text{ m}^2}$
<i>Length</i>	Path Length	km
<i>N-Length</i>	Normalized Path Length	$\frac{\text{m}}{1000 \text{ m}^2}$
<i>Time</i>	Estimated execution time (3 m/s speed & 1 sec delay/turn)	min

Table 4.2. *Evaluation metrics*

boundaries of the ROIs or the NGZs. As expected, BCM achieves higher *PoC* than both the core method and GCM. To do that, since the paths are allowed to get out of the boundaries of the ROIs, it is rational that the *Turns* and *Length* are increased, something that has also impact on the missions' *Time*, which is also increased. Finally, the *PoOC* also presents a small increase, something that is caused by the excessive length of paths in the marginal areas of the ROI. Regarding CCM, it manages to fulfill its main objective, i.e., to provide complete coverage for any type of ROI, no matter how complex-shaped it is. Due to the cropping of paths, and the violation of the constant d_s , the *PoOC* and the *Turns* are significantly increased compared to the other coverage modes. The overall paths' *Length* and operational *Time* is increased compared to both the core method and GCM, something that was expected due to the rationale of the methodology, however, it is smaller than the one for BCM. This happens mostly because of the larger areas' ROIs, where the cropping and the increased complexity of paths met in CCM have a smaller impact on *Length* and *Time* than the excessive paths' length generated in BCM, that gets outside of the boundaries of the ROI.

From the average evaluation's results, the radar chart is generated (figure 4.12), which qualitatively presents the features of each coverage mode. At a glance, one can see that the core method -mentioned as SotA- and GCM have almost identical features, and outmatch the other two modes in terms of resources' efficiency, but they fall short in the achieved coverage (which, however, even for them is higher than 95.5%). On the other hand, CCM and BCM are significantly improved in terms of achieved coverage, however, to achieve that they have to sacrifice part of the resource-efficiency features.

Figure 4.12. Modes' ranking.
 *SotA refers to the method presented in chapter 3

Table 4.4 and figure 4.13 present the evaluation results in testbed #2, and Table 4.5 and Figure 4.14 the results in testbed #3. For these ROIs all conclusions discussed above for the average metrics of the overall evaluation are valid, except for the last one, i.e., the one regarding the *Length* and *Time* comparison between BCM and GCM. In both examples, the area of the ROI and specifically the perimeter of the boundaries is small enough, so the excessive paths' length

Metrics	Core Method	GCM	BCM	CCM
<i>PoC</i>	95.92%	95.79%	98.95%	99.97%
<i>PoOC</i>	51.90%	52.23%	53.28%	59.67%
<i>Turns</i>	75.35	75.65	79.65	103.50
<i>N-Turns</i>	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.18
<i>Length</i>	21,799.96	21,799.95	33,895.96	26,753.30
<i>N-Length</i>	23.69	23.66	39.17	30.86
<i>Time</i>	122.37	122.37	189.64	150.35

Table 4.3. Simulated evaluation average results

generated in BCM has a smaller impact than CCM's path complexity on these two metrics. It can be seen though, that for testbed #3, which is a lot larger than testbed #2, the gap between these metrics for CCM and BCM is smaller than the one met in testbed #2. As the area and perimeter of a ROI get larger, CCM takes the lead and achieves a smaller path's length than BCM. Figures 4.13 and 4.14 present the heatmaps of coverage for the two benchmark ROIs and are very indicative examples of how each mode handles such cases to achieve the targeted results and objectives.

Metrics	Core Method	GCM	BCM	CCM
<i>PoC</i>	94.19%	95.24%	97.33%	100.00%
<i>PoOC</i>	49.68%	48.63%	50.07%	87.30%
<i>Turns</i>	8	8	12	25
<i>N-Turns</i>	0.21	0.21	0.32	0.67
<i>Length</i>	800.00	799.99	1119.99	1744.89
<i>N-Length</i>	21.44	21.44	30.02	46.77
<i>Time</i>	4.58	4.58	6.42	10.11

Table 4.4. *Simulated evaluation results - testbed #2.*

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter has presented the development of three novel coverage modes, building upon presented in the previous one. The introduction of these new modes intends to show that the common problems faced when applying grid-based methods in real-world conditions can be overcome, and lays the path towards a wider application of such methods in real-life applications. The performance and efficiency of the modes are proved via extensive simulated evaluations and a comparison with another SoA CPP method. The outcome of this work is a CPP method with three ad-hoc coverage modes, each incorporating features that make it more appropriate for specific types of operations, which build upon the SoA and improve it in certain aspects. This CPP method is appropriate for use with any UAV capable of following a pre-defined route, and ensuring the demanded overlap in the collected data makes it highly efficient for RS operations. In addition to that, the elaborate presentation of the

Figure 4.13. Modes evaluation in testbed #2

methodology and the ideas used to reach the expected outcome can work as a guide for the application of different grid-based path-planning approaches in real-world problems.

Metrics	Core Method	GCM	BCM	CCM
<i>PoC</i>	95.71%	95.85%	99.32%	99.98%
<i>PoOC</i>	53.44%	53.51%	54.19%	60.26%
<i>Turns</i>	63	64	72	83
<i>N-Turns</i>	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.14
<i>Length</i>	13,759.99	13,759.98	16,159.98	18,044.70
<i>N-Length</i>	23.87	23.87	28.03	31.30
<i>Time</i>	77.49	77.51	90.98	101.63

Table 4.5. Simulated evaluation results - testbed #3.

Figure 4.14. Modes evaluation in testbed #3

5

The Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions Problem

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5.1 Introduction

In UAVs' RS operations, there are certain cases where it is required to inspect (i) multiple non-connected regions, (ii) in the shortest amount of time possible, and (iii) the resolution of the collected data is important, but not critical, given that they respect a lower limit. Such applications could include security infrastructure inspections, agricultural inspections for certain policies (i.e., EU-CAP [103]) or receiving funds, and emergency site assessments. While satellite imagery could fulfill some of these needs -as also discussed in introduction- major limitations exist, including (i) the very-low resolution (compared to UAV data), (ii) the inability to collect data on-demand or in real-time, and (iii) the high data acquisition and processing cost.

To the best of our knowledge, at the moment this work is written, there are no works available in literature with the objective to capture a single representative image of multiple disjoint ROIs during a single UAV flight. The most common approach used in such cases is CPP, where (i) either scanning a wider region -including all the sub-ROIs- to obtain the desired data is involved, leading though to waste of resources (i.e., time and energy) to also scan large areas that are of no interest, or (ii) TSP-CPP methods are applied in disjoint ROIs, scanning each of them separately, and determining the visitation order using a TSP solution to make the procedure more efficient. While neither CPP, nor TSP-CPP methods can be considered as directly related to the work introduced in this paper, these two, along with human-defined points of interest (POIs) to be visited by a UAV, are the approaches that can be used as alternatives to fulfill (not optimally) the objectives of the aforementioned problem.

5.1.1 Contributions

In the context of this work, a new path planning problem regarding the fast inspection of scattered regions utilizing UAVs -the FISR problem- is identified and defined in detail, and a novel approach for multi-UAV Disjoint Areas' Inspection -the mUDAI method- that fulfills the objectives of this problem is proposed. The main objective of the proposed work is to balance the trade-off between the resolution of the captured data, and the time needed for the UAV(s) to perform this task. To achieve that, a methodology that allows the UAV(s) to capture a single, yet comprehensive, photo of each ROI is proposed, and trajectories that allow the fast and efficient visitation of all the defined regions are generated, in a way that (i) they respect the operational capabilities and limitations of the UAVs participating in the mission, and (ii) they facilitate in the saving of resources such as operational time and energy consumed during the procedure. Figure 5.1 presents an indicative example of an FISR task.

Figure 5.1. *Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions task. Two UAVs tasked with inspecting 10 disjoint regions: (a) User-defined waypoints allow fast operation but lack path optimization and fair task assignment, while also leading to random ROI captures. (b) CPP planning ensures high-quality captures but introduces superfluous data and long-duration operations. (c) Our mUDAI method balances speed, comprehensiveness, and efficiency, overcoming these hurdles effectively.*

The red polygons correspond to the ROIs that need to be inspected, the blue rectangles correspond to the area captured by the UAVs' sensors, and the colorful lines correspond to the trajectories that the UAV(s) should follow. In 5.1(a), the capturing positions, flight's altitude, and visitation order are user-defined parameters, leading to incomplete, or unnecessary surrounding areas' coverage, and inefficient management of operational resources (i.e., time and energy). In 5.1(b), all ROIs are covered completely, in a uniform way, however, resources are wasted to cover huge areas outside the designated regions. Finally, 5.1(c) presents the mUDAI method's solution, providing balanced length of trajectories, and the highest resolution per ROI, that ensures complete coverage.

5.1.2 Chapter Outline

The rest of this work is organized as follows: section 5.2 strictly defines the FISR problem, section 5.3 presents the introduced methodology - mUDAI, section 5.4 is about the evaluation of the proposed method by presenting results out of two sets of real-world experiments, and finally, section 5.5 summarizes this work and discusses thoughts and outcomes.

5.2 Problem Definition: Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions (FISR)

This section formulates the FISR problem, i.e., collecting the best possible images from spatially disjoint ROIs in the minimum possible time utilizing UAVs.

5.2.1 The Setup

Assuming a user-defined set of k ROIs that should be inspected:

$$\mathcal{R} = \{R_1, \dots, R_k\} \quad (5.1)$$

Each i th ROI is defined in a Cartesian space as: $R_i = [r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{p_i}]$, where $r_j = [x, y] \in \mathbb{R}^2, \forall j \in [1, 2, \dots, p_i]$ ¹.

5.2.2 Decision Variables

Consider a team of n UAVs, each executing a trajectory τ_i , defined as:

$$\tau_i = [T_1^i, T_2^i, \dots, T_{m_i}^i], \quad T_j^i \in \{\chi_j^i\} \cup \{v_j^i\},$$

where:

- $\chi_j^i = [x, y, z] \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents a **navigation waypoint**, strictly used for UAV movement between locations, with:
 - x, y specifying the coordinates in the 2D Cartesian plane, and
 - z denoting the altitude relative to the ground.
- $v_j^i = [\chi_j^i, s_j^i]$ represents a **viewpoint**, where:
 - $\chi_j^i = [x, y, z]$ specifies the position of the UAV, and
 - s_j^i denotes a set of controllable variables for the UAV's sensor at that position, used for data collection.

The union of navigation waypoints (χ_j^i) and viewpoints (v_j^i) defines the trajectory elements T_j^i :

$$T_j^i = \chi_j^i \cup v_j^i,$$

where:

¹Please note that any other coordinates' system is also compatible with such definition and only a translation will be needed.

- χ_j^i exists for all $j \in [1, 2, \dots, m^i]$,
- v_j^i is defined only for those positions where data collection occurs.

Thus, the trajectory τ_i integrates both:

$$\tau_i = \bigcup_{j=1}^{m^i} T_j^i,$$

allowing the UAV to combine navigation tasks and data collection.

$$\tau := [\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n] \quad (5.2)$$

For each τ_i trajectory the viewpoints v_i positions will determine the data acquisition specifics. The trajectories τ_i and the corresponding waypoints positions χ_j^i which serve as the navigational components cannot be set arbitrary, but they need to satisfy a set of operational constraints. More specifically:

1. $T(\tau_i) \leq t_{\max}, \forall i \in [1, 2, \dots, n]$, where $T(\tau_i)$ denotes the time needed to execute τ_i trajectory and t_{\max} is a maximum operational duration - inline with the battery capabilities of each i th UAV.
2. $\|\chi_{j+1}^i - \chi_j^i\| \leq u_{\max} dt, \forall i \in [1, 2, \dots, n], j \in [1, 2, \dots, m_i - 1]$, where u_{\max} denotes the maximum speed the UAVs are allowed to travel and dt the time needed to reach χ_{j+1}^i from χ_j^i .
3. $a_{\min} \leq \chi_j^i(3) \leq a_{\max}, \forall i \in [1, 2, \dots, n], j \in [1, 2, \dots, m_i]$ where a_{\min}, a_{\max} denote the minimum and maximum altitude a UAV is allowed to reach (due to hardware, or user-defined limitations, and legislation) respectively.
4. the UAVs carry sensors with certain specifications (i.e., horizontal field of view (hFOV), vertical field of view (vFOV), horizontal resolution (hRes), vertical resolution (vRes), etc. [104]).

The previously defined constraints can be, in general, represented as a system of inequalities:

$$\mathcal{C}(\tau) \leq 0 \quad (5.3)$$

where \mathcal{C} is a set of nonlinear functions of the decision variables τ .

5.2.3 Measurements - Collected Images

After the execution of the corresponding τ_i , for each i th UAV, and in each viewpoint v_j^i , an image $I_j^i \in \mathbb{R}^2, \forall j \in [1, 2, \dots, l_i]^2$ is captured, forming the

²Take into consideration that $l_i \leq m_i, \forall i \in [1, 2, \dots, n]$

measurements' vector:

$$\mathbf{y}_i = [I_1^i, I_2^i, \dots, I_n^i], \forall i \in [1, 2, \dots, n]$$

The augmented measurements' vector for all the mission, taking into account all UAVs, is comprised as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} := [\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_n] \quad (5.4)$$

5.2.4 Objective Function

The objective of the FISR problem is to acquire the best possible representation of the user-defined set of k ROIs (5.1). After the collection of image data (5.4), a set of ROIs - Images pairs can be formed:

$$Q_i(\mathbf{y}) = \{R_i, J(R_i)\}, \forall i \in [1, 2, \dots, k] \quad (5.5)$$

where $J(R_i)$ denotes the corresponding image for R_i . For each k pair, $J(Q_i)$ denotes a score that quantifies the *completeness* and *accuracy* of representation of R_i from $J(R_i)$. It is assumed that for a perfect alignment and representation of i th ROI, the corresponding $J(Q_i) = 0$, therefore $J \in [0, \infty)$. The overall representation score can be defined as:

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{i=1}^k J(Q_i(\mathbf{y}))$$

It is desirable to achieve the best possible score in the minimum possible time, therefore the overall objective of the FISR problem is as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\tau}) = \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{y}) + \alpha \sum_i^n T(\tau_i) \quad (5.6)$$

The positive constant α serves as a weight for giving less or more priority to one of the objectives.

5.2.5 FISR Optimization Problem

Given the mathematical description presented above, the problem of choosing the decision variables (5.2) for a team of UAVs, to capture in the best possible way a set of ROIs (5.1), in the minimum possible time, can be described as the following constrained optimization problem:

$$\text{minimize } (5.6) \quad (5.7)$$

$$\text{subject to } (5.3)$$

5.3 multi-UAV Disjoint Areas Inspection (mUDAI) Methodology

5.3.1 Overview of the Approach

Below, we describe how the proposed methodology directly aligns with and extends the previous problem formulation. Recall that the FISR problem defined in Section 5.2 seeks to determine the UAV trajectories τ (Eq. (5.2)) and the corresponding viewpoints v_i that minimize the overall cost function $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}, \tau)$ (Eq. (5.6)). The cost incorporates both the quality of the collected imagery from the set of ROIs, captured in $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{y})$, and the mission duration. Additionally, all such solutions must satisfy the constraints $\mathcal{C}(\tau) \leq 0$ (Eq. (5.3)) that stem from operational and hardware limitations.

Our proposed *mUDAI* methodology addresses this problem in a structured, two-stage approach:

1. **Viewpoint Optimization:** We first focus on selecting a single optimal viewpoint for each ROI, ensuring that the image I_j^i acquired at this viewpoint provides a high-quality representation $\mathcal{J}(R_i)$ for the corresponding ROI R_i (Eq. (5.5)).
2. **Trajectory Optimization:** Once the optimal viewpoints are computed, the second step involves the optimization of trajectories τ that connect the UAVs' initial positions to the selected viewpoints v_i , and then back to a designated endpoint.

Our approach effectively combines two distinct optimization strategies: one for determining the best photo capture positions and another for planning optimal UAV flight routes. This two-step setup provides both precise data capture and efficient navigation. A schematic overview of the mUDAI's pipeline is depicted in Figure 5.2.

5.3.2 Optimization Scheme

Viewpoint Optimization

The primary goal of the mUDAI algorithm is to optimize the capture process while considering flight constraints. By focusing on a single viewpoint per ROI, the complexity of selecting multiple overlapping or redundant viewpoints is reduced. This viewpoint selection process aligns directly with minimizing the image-related portion of the objective $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{y})$ and, ultimately, the total objective $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}, \tau)$.

Figure 5.2. *mUDAI methodology splits the FISR problem in two discrete optimization sub-problems - as a first step, given the ROIs and the specifications of the camera used, dual-annealing algorithm is utilized for the calculation of the optimal viewpoints, given the optimization objectives - as a second step, a VRP solver is used for the calculation of the optimal visitation order, respecting the energy constraints of the UAVs.*

To find these optimal viewpoints, we leverage the UAV's camera model and the ROI's geometric representation. Figure 4.1 visualizes the projection of the region R_i on the captured image, where I_j^i corresponds to a box of d_h length and d_v width (according to equations 4.1, 4.2). More formally, for each ROI R_i (Eq. 5.1), our objective is to determine a viewing pose $v_j^i = [x_j^i, s_j^i] = [x, y, z, \theta]$ that maximizes $J(Q_i(\mathbf{y}))$ during scene imaging. Specifically, we aim to find:

$$v_j^i = \arg \max_{v_j^i} J(Q_i(\mathbf{y})) \quad (5.8)$$

subject to the altitude and camera model constraints from $\mathcal{C}(\tau)$.

To achieve this, we consider two possible optimization metrics, which can be directly substituted into $J(Q_i)$:

1. Maximized Coverage Objective (MCO): Ensures each ROI is completely captured in a single photo, minimizing the inclusion of areas outside the intended target.
2. Balanced Coverage Objective (BCO): Seeks a compromise between capturing the entire ROI and reducing the capture of extraneous space, focusing instead on high-resolution captures of significant ROI's portions.

The first objective, denoted as MCO, prioritizes maximizing the overlap between the ROI and the camera capture. When this overlap is maximized, indicating that the entire ROI is contained within the camera capture, an additional penalty term is introduced to penalize large captures. This penalty is applied only when the whole ROI is contained within the capture, ensuring

that the capture is as small as possible while still fully covering the ROI. MCO is computed using the formula

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{MCO}}(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)}{\mathbf{R}_i} & \text{if } \frac{\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)}{\mathbf{R}_i} < 1 \\ \frac{\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)}{\mathbf{R}_i} + \frac{1}{\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)} & \text{otherwise } \left(\frac{\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)}{\mathbf{R}_i} = 1 \right) \end{cases} \quad (5.9)$$

The second objective, BCO, assigns equal weight to both the intersection and union of the target ROI and camera capture, resembling the popular Intersection over Union (IoU) metric used in various applications. To calculate BCO we apply the formula

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{BCO}}(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)}{\mathbf{R}_i \cup \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{R}_i)} \quad (5.10)$$

Figure 5.3 showcases the results of the two objectives for the same ROI. By considering these objectives, mUDAI can capture the entire parcel, or focus on obtaining high-resolution imagery of the most informative areas, while minimizing the impact of any exterior noise. This adaptability allows for efficient and effective capture planning in various scenarios.

Figure 5.3. Illustrative comparison of MCO and BCO optimization objectives. The blue polygon represents the ROI, while the red polygon indicates the camera capture area. In MCO, the objective is to fully capture the defined ROI while minimizing the area outside the ROI. In contrast, BCO strikes a balance between capturing the ROI and reducing coverage of areas outside the ROI, achieving a lower GSD and minimizing extraneous coverage.

For each \mathbf{R}_i , we solve a different optimization problem using the following optimization objectives³. For the optimization procedure, we employ the dual-annealing algorithm. Dual-annealing operates by iteratively adjusting the

³Therefore, the objective functions defined below are going to be calculated and optimized separately for each \mathbf{R}_i . By doing so, we reduce the complexity of the original combinatorial problem as defined in 5.7, without jeopardizing the quality of the solution.

position and orientation of the UAV in each direction, which includes longitude (x), latitude (y), altitude (z), and yaw angle (θ) to achieve the best photo capture.

The inputs consist of: 1) an Objective Function, which is the function to be optimized by taking a set of input parameters $[x, y, z, \theta]$ and returning the objective value; 2) an Initial Solution $[x_0, y_0, z_0, \theta_0]$, which serves as the starting point for the optimization process; and 3) Bounds for each input parameter $[x_b, y_b, z_b, \theta_b]$, which are to limit the permissible range of values for these parameters. The bounds are defined as follows:

- x_b : The range of allowable values for the x -coordinate of the UAV's position. It is determined by the $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ of the ROI's polygon.
- y_b : The range of allowable values for the y -coordinate of the UAV's position. It is determined by the $[y_{\min}, y_{\max}]$ of the ROI's polygon.
- z_b : The range of allowable values for the altitude of the UAV. It is bounded between the minimum altitude $[a_{\min}]$ and the maximum altitude $[a_{\max}]$, two user-defined parameters that may derive either from the topology of the region, or the flight regulations.
- θ_b : The range of allowable values for the parameter theta, which represents the heading of the UAV. In our implementation it is bounded between 0 and 180 degrees.

By utilizing the dual-annealing algorithm with the appropriate inputs, the optimization process can efficiently explore the solution space and find the optimal configuration that maximizes the $J(Q_i)$ score based on the defined constraints and bounds (part of $\mathcal{C}(\tau)$).

Trajectory Optimization

VRP is a fundamental optimization problem in logistics and transportation. In VRP, a fleet of vehicles is tasked with delivering goods or servicing various locations. Each location has its own demand or service requirement, and the objective is to find the most efficient routes for the vehicles to fulfill all demands while optimizing factors such as distance traveled and vehicle utilization.

In our case, the VRP problem is time-constrained, as the battery capacity constraint directly translates into the number of parcels that a UAV can capture in a single flight. The UAV's battery capacity limits the distance it can cover and the duration it can stay operational during the inspection mission. Therefore, the routing problem in FISR involves finding the optimal paths for the UAVs to

inspect the scattered regions or parcels while ensuring that the battery capacity is not exceeded.

More precisely, this step determines the order and allocation of ROIs to UAVs, aiming to:

$$\min_{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n} \alpha \sum_i T(\tau_i) \quad \text{subject to } \mathcal{C}(\tau) \leq 0. \quad (5.11)$$

By integrating the results from the viewpoint optimization stage, the VRP ensures each R_i is inspected at its chosen viewpoint v_j^i . The resulting set of trajectories τ_i respects the maximum speed, altitude, and time constraints and positions the UAVs to capture high-quality images effectively.

To solve this problem, we utilized the Google OR-tools⁴. OR-Tools is a powerful and versatile optimization software suite designed to address complex optimization problems related to vehicle routing, flows, integer and linear programming, and constraint programming. The existing software underwent considerable modifications to align with our specific requirements, particularly addressing two critical areas: path generation and efficient UAV deployment.

Firstly, the application was adapted to incorporate constraints that factor in the maximum distance the UAV can cover. This ensures that the generated paths are within the operational capacity of the UAV. The algorithm calculates the distances between all the parcels and the initial position, which is crucial for optimizing travel time. The initial position is selected to be as centrally located as possible among the ROIs, thereby minimizing unnecessary travel and simplifying the launch and return phases. Since the UAVs start and end their journeys at this same location, the flight paths form a closed loop.

The VRP solution is initially computed given the current number of available UAVs. If the resulting route segments exceed the UAVs' battery capabilities, the route is then split into twice as many segments for the next attempt. In other words, a single UAV's route is subdivided into two segments if needed; if there are three UAVs in use, their three individual routes become six upon splitting. This doubling process continues until each resulting segment fits within the UAVs' operational battery limits, ensuring that the mission remains both feasible and efficient.

Our approach supports a multi-UAV setup that operates in parallel by assigning distinct navigation altitudes for each UAV. This prevents potential collisions when UAVs travel diagonally between viewpoints as demonstrated in Figure 5.4. Each UAV travels at a unique altitude between viewpoints, adjusts its altitude and orientation upon reaching a viewpoint to capture the ROI, and then resumes its assigned navigation altitude to travel to the next viewpoint. This process ensures safe and efficient operation, eliminating the risk of collision.

⁴<https://developers.google.com/optimization>

Figure 5.4. The inclusion of intermediate navigational waypoints in UAV trajectories, enabling transitions at constant altitudes unique to each UAV, ensures safe and collision-free operations. On the left side of the figure, a trajectory directly connecting the viewpoints is shown, which includes intersecting trajectories leading to a potential collision point, whereas on the right side, the introduction of intermediate waypoints has eliminated the presence of potential collision points.

5.4 Experiments

5.4.1 Experimental Setup

For the deployment of the mUDAI methodology in real-world scenarios, a setup similar to the one described in section 3, and the platform presented in appendix B, was used. Specifically, a set of commercial UAVs⁵, along with an updated version of the custom Android application developed for this purpose were used to execute all missions presented in sub-sections 5.4.2 and 5.4.3. Figure 5.5 shows the exact hardware setup used for the deployment of the missions.

5.4.2 Small-scale Mission in Galatsi, Athens

This scenario consists of two separate mission deployments, in the same area, for the exact same five (5) ROIs to be inspected, using the two different optimization objectives for the calculation of the optimal viewpoint (MCO, BCO) in each of them. For the deployment of these missions a single UAV was used.

As shown in figure 5.6(a), the user defines the FISR problem to be solved by selecting the ROIs and the initial position for the deployment of the UAV.

⁵<https://www.dji.com/phantom-4-pro>

Figure 5.5. *Experimental hardware setup used to validate the performance of the mUDAI algorithm. The setup includes a standard laptop and two commercial UAVs, each equipped with controllers running custom Android applications designed for mission execution and data collection.*

Additionally, they define the minimum and the maximum flight altitude allowed for the viewpoints, and the designated flight altitude for the transition among these positions, the optimization objective that should be used for the calculation of the viewpoints, the number of UAVs that they intend to use, and the desired UAV speed, needed for the time estimation of the missions.

The main objectives of the mission deployments in this scenario is to visually explain the difference between MCO and BCO, to discuss the errors and deviations introduced in the collected data, and to provide a validation for the time estimation of the missions, a parameter critical for their safe deployment, since each mission should always respect the nominal operational duration of the UAVs used.

As shown in figure 5.6(b) and 5.6(c), MCO objective indeed calculates viewpoints that contain the whole ROIs, while simultaneously minimizing the area of non-designated regions in the camera capture, and BCO objective calculates viewpoints that allow for an image capture containing a large amount of -but not the whole- ROIs, managing this way to exclude larger amount of non-designated areas from the camera capture. From the overlaid collected data over the map, it is clear that there is a small deviation among the calculated camera captures and the collected data. This deviation is mostly caused by four (4) factors: i) the drone's camera gimbal not facing vertically to the ground surface (87° is the max allowed angle for the equipment used), ii) errors in the map that the regions were initially defined, iii) GPS errors, iv) deviations caused by wind gusts during the captures. Finally, regarding the deviation between the

Figure 5.6. Real-world deployment of *mUDAI* solutions on testbed #1, shown on a base map that provides geographic context for the area, with overlaid collected data. (a) *FISR*: The initial problem formulation with user-defined ROIs (black polygons) and the UAV's deployment position (red pin). (b) *MCO*: The optimized solution that ensures image captures containing the whole ROIs, where the calculated camera captures are illustrated with blue polygons, and the collected data are overlaid on the map. (c) *BCO*: The optimized solution that provides lower GSD in the collected images, but does not capture the whole ROIs, with the camera captures similarly illustrated by blue polygons, and the collected data overlaid on the map. In both (b) and (c), the trajectories, shown as connecting lines, represent the paths calculated by the VRP solver.

estimated and the real-world mission duration, as shown in table 5.1, for the MCO mission deployment the real-world duration was 5.56% smaller, and for the

BCO 4.35% smaller than the estimated ones. It is worth mentioning that having a slightly larger estimated than real-world mission duration is more desired than the opposite, since it provides a larger time margin for the safe return of the UAV to the base position, after the completion of the data collection.

Time	Estimated	Real-world	Deviation
<i>MCO</i>	4.14 min	3.91 min	5.56%
<i>BCO</i>	4.14 min	3.96 min	4.35%

Table 5.1. *Experimental results in testbed #1*

5.4.3 Large-scale Mission in “The Ghost City of Chortiatis”, Thessaloniki

This scenario compares the use of a typical mCPP method [105, 106], deploying two UAVs to collect data out of the desired ROIs, with the use of mUDAI method for the same objective, using one and two UAVs in separate deployments. Figure 5.7(a) shows the FISR problem, as defined by the user over a map. In order to collect data out of these ROIs using a CPP method, with a flight altitude of 40m, a percentage of sidelap among sequential images of 75% to successfully compose an orthomosaic of the covered region, and a UAV speed of 3m/s to allow for collection of non-corrupted images, the estimated mission duration for a single UAV is 35.5 minutes. This value exceeds the nominal operational duration of the UAV used, which is 25 minutes, making the deployment of two UAVs for the CPP mission mandatory. Regarding the mUDAI methodology, for a more detailed comparison the mission is deployed two times, one with a single UAV, since the mission’s duration is smaller than the nominal operational duration of the UAV, and one with two UAVs, as in the CPP run. For both mUDAI deployments, the MCO optimization objective was used.

This experiment compares missions’ duration and areas’ coverage in all deployments, and presents the average GSD for each mission. To allow for a qualitative comparison of the collected data, the coverage results are presented by using the commonly known metrics for retrieval tasks: Recall and Precision. Recall measures how much of the desired area was actually covered. It is calculated by dividing the correctly covered area (true positives) by the total area that should have been covered (true positives plus false negatives). Precision, on the other hand, measures how accurate the coverage was, indicating how much of the area that was covered was supposed to be covered. It is calculated by dividing the correctly covered area (true positives) by the total area that was

Figure 5.7. Real-world deployment of *mCPP* and *mUDAI* solutions on testbed #2, shown on a base map providing geographic context for the area, with overlaid collected data. (a) *FISR*: The initial problem formulation with user-defined ROIs (red polygons) and UAV deployment position (red pin). (b) *mCPP*: The ROI outlined by a black polygon, with the collected data processed to generate an orthomosaic - displayed on the map with a yellowish outline. (c) *mUDAI - 1 UAV*: The optimized solution for a single UAV, where the blue polygons represent the calculated camera captures, and the collected data are overlaid on the map - with a yellowish outline. (d) *mUDAI - 2 UAVs*: A multi-UAV solution, illustrating distributed trajectories, camera captures (blue polygons), and the collected data (with a yellowish outline). In (b), (c), and (d), the colorful lines represent the trajectories calculated by the *CPP* algorithm and the *VRP* solver, respectively.

covered (true positives plus false positives). These metrics are included in table 5.2 for all mission deployments. Additionally, figure 5.7 presents the defined FISR problem (5.7(a)), and the trajectories along with the overlaid collected data for all three deployments (5.7(b) - 5.7(d)).

	Time	Coverage Recall	Coverage Precision	Average GSD
<i>mCPP</i>	18.5 min	100%	5%	1.09 cm/px*
<i>mUDAI</i>				
<i>1 UAV</i>	10.0 min	99.3%	59.8%	0.68 cm/px
<i>mUDAI</i>				
<i>2 UAVs</i>	5.5 min	99.3%	59.8%	0.68 cm/px

Table 5.2. *Experimental results in testbed #2*

* While this value should be true and constant for a CPP mission deployed on a flat ground surface, since the operational altitude of the mission is not adjusted according to the topology of the region, this is just a theoretical value and does not correspond to the real GSD of the collected data.

The results demonstrate that while both mCPP and mUDAI achieve nearly identical coverage recall (100% for mCPP and 99.3% for mUDAI - where this small deviation is caused by the real-world errors introduced during mission deployments, as discussed in the previous sub-section), mUDAI significantly outperforms mCPP in avoiding the collection of superfluous data. mCPP has a very low coverage precision of just 5%, meaning a large portion of the captured data includes non-designated areas. In contrast, mUDAI -with both 1 and 2 UAVs- improves precision dramatically to 59.8%, as it minimizes unnecessary data collection by focusing more effectively on the desired areas. Finally, while mCPP could potentially achieve a similar or even better GSD, doing so would require a significant increase in mission time.

Reducing irrelevant data collection is crucial for efficient post-processing, saving time and computational resources (for the generation of the orthomosaic, more than 3.5 hours were needed). mUDAI, especially with multiple UAVs, not only completes missions faster but also improves data quality by minimizing unnecessary captures. This precision enhances resource management, leading to quicker analysis and lower energy consumption, aligning with mUDAI's goal of optimizing UAVs' mission efficiency.

5.5 Conclusion

This work introduced the FISR problem and proposed a novel solution: the mUDAI methodology. Through extensive experimentation in both small and large-scale real-world scenarios, we demonstrated the effectiveness of mUDAI in optimizing UAV flight paths for the rapid inspection of multiple scattered regions. The results from the experiments clearly demonstrate the advantages of mUDAI over standard CPP techniques, particularly in missions where time efficiency is critical. By minimizing the area of non-designated regions in the UAV's camera captures and optimizing the UAVs' trajectories, mUDAI proved capable of completing missions faster, while also being more efficient in terms of resources management, such as energy consumption, and computational time/-cost needed for results' processing. The work presented in this chapter is highly appropriate for applications like disaster response, fire evolution monitoring, critical infrastructure monitoring, and precision agriculture.

6

Conclusion & Future Directions

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6.1 Conclusion

In the context of this dissertation, the problem of efficiently generating routes for multiple UAVs to perform remote sensing operations has been addressed. Specifically, great effort has been given towards combining commercial platforms' ease of use and maturity level, with SoA features regarding the effectiveness in data collection, and efficiency in managing operational resources like time and energy. The presented methodologies respect the limitations of the UAVs used, and take into account their specifications, and the real-world factors that can affect their operation. By enabling multi-UAV deployment, the major limiting factor in multi-copter UAV operations -that is their reduced operational duration- is mitigated, allowing to scan larger areas in the same amount of time. Additionally, time critical operations like SAR missions, and the detection of moving objects of interest like vehicles, or humans in need, are handled a lot more efficiently thanks to the simultaneous deployment of several sensors in different places. The presented solutions have been tested in both simulated setups and real-world operations, proving their efficiency, effectiveness, robustness and readiness level.

The contributions of this dissertation can be summarized as follows:

- A multi-UAV coverage mission planning platform for RS operations has been introduced, combining SoA efficiency with commercial ease of use in deploying real-world missions. This work introduces a novel optimization scheme, based on simulated annealing algorithm, for applying efficiently grid-based path planning methodologies in real-world ROIs. For the multi-UAV functionality, a SoA area division algorithm is modified to support proportional area allocation -to allow the simultaneous use of heterogeneous vehicles- and used to divide the overall ROI to exclusive sub-regions for each UAV. A simple heuristic that significantly reduces the number of turns in the generated trajectories is applied to the STC algorithm, that is used to calculate coverage paths. The result of this work is a powerful mCPP methodology, ready for use in real-world conditions, that supports very complex shaped ROIs with NFZs inside, provides almost complete coverage, and manages efficiently the operational resources. This method is extensively validated in a simulated setup, and compared with another SoA CPP method, and a multi-agent marginal utility study is performed to explain when and how the utilization of multiple UAVs is beneficiary on the field. Finally, two real-world deployments in indicative precision agriculture and SAR scenarios are performed.
- Building upon the previous work, a set of heuristics are introduced to overcome the remaining issues that usually appear when applying grid-based path planning methods to real-world operations. Such issues are caused by the discretization error introduced during the representation of the actual ROI on grid, making the problem that is solved different from the real one. The result of this work is a powerful CPP methodology that inherits all the benefits of the core method, and resolves all the remaining issues, providing additionally three ad-hoc coverage modes that are appropriate for different types of operations and vehicles, depending on the missions' needs and restrictions. The introduced methodology is extensively evaluated in the same setup with the core method, for comparison reasons, proving its efficiency and effectiveness, while managing to achieve all of the claimed benefits.
- The new Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions (FISR) problem is identified and described in detail. This new path planning problem for multi-copter UAVs describes the need of effectively inspecting multiple disjoint areas with one or more UAVs, in the shortest amount of time possible. As a solution to this newly described problem, the multi-UAV Disjoint Areas' Inspection (mUDAI) algorithm is introduced, that deals with the global

FISR problem as two discrete optimization sub-problems, one for the calculation of the optimal viewpoint, given a specific objective, and one for the calculation of the most efficient visitation order for these viewpoints, in a way that respects the operational duration of the UAVs, and any other restrictions may be enforced by the user, vehicle, environment, or legal framework. For the validation of the introduced method two sets of real-world deployments have been performed, to provide a comparison between the two different optimization objectives for the viewpoints' calculation, and a comparison with a mCPP methodology used to fulfill the objectives of the defined FISR problem.

6.2 Future Directions

The methodologies presented in this dissertation have laid a strong foundation for efficient multi-UAV RS operations, yet opportunities for further advancements remain. One promising direction is the integration of on-board processing capabilities that enable UAVs to dynamically adjust their trajectories in response to real-time environmental changes and unforeseen parameters. By leveraging advancements in edge computing and sensor fusion, UAVs could autonomously adapt to varying conditions such as unexpected obstacles, or dynamically changing operational environments, further enhancing their robustness and operational efficiency.

Another aspect that warrants further research is the development of solutions for operating in GPS-denied environments. Such environments pose unique challenges for UAV navigation, requiring alternative approaches like visual odometry (VO) and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) techniques. Enabling navigation in GPS-denied environments would unlock new possibilities for deploying UAVs in dense urban areas, forested regions, and underground environments, where traditional navigation systems would fail. Developing robust and efficient visual SLAM frameworks tailored to multi-UAV systems would be an essential step toward achieving this capability.

Finally, expanding UAV operations to indoor environments introduces the need for advanced collision avoidance and exploration mechanisms in spaces with dynamic and unpredictable obstacles. By utilizing SoA computer vision (CV) techniques and navigational solutions, UAVs could navigate in complex indoor spaces while maintaining robust situational awareness. This includes detecting and avoiding moving obstacles, exploring unknown environments efficiently, and collaborating with other UAVs in confined spaces. These capabilities are crucial for a wide range of applications, such as warehouse management, industrial inspections, and indoor SAR missions.

6.3 Publications from this Dissertation

a. Journal Publications

- (1) Gkelios, S., **Apostolidis, S. D.**, Kapoutsis, P. C., Kapoutsis, A. C., & Kosmatopoulos, E. B. (2025). Beyond Coverage Path Planning: Can UAV Swarms Perfect Scattered Regions Inspections? *Submitted for publication in Robotics and Autonomous Systems*.
- (2) Stefanopoulou, A., Raptis, E. K., **Apostolidis, S. D.**, Gkelios, S., Kapoutsis, A. C., Chatzichristofis, S. A., ... & Kosmatopoulos, E. B. (2024). Improving time and energy efficiency in multi-UAV coverage operations by optimizing the UAVs' initial positions. *International Journal of Intelligent Robotics and Applications*, 1-19.
- (3) **Apostolidis, S. D.**, Vougiatzis, G., Kapoutsis, A. C., Chatzichristofis, S. A., & Kosmatopoulos, E. B. (2023). Systematically improving the efficiency of grid-based coverage path planning methodologies in real-world uavs' operations. *Drones*, 7(6), 399.
- (4) **Apostolidis, S. D.**, Kapoutsis, P. C., Kapoutsis, A. C., & Kosmatopoulos, E. B. (2022). Cooperative multi-UAV coverage mission planning platform for remote sensing applications. *Autonomous Robots*, 46(2), 373-400.

b. Conference Proceedings

- (1) Maglione, G. L., Berretta, L., Godfrey, S. B., **Apostolidis, S.**, Kapoutsis, A., Kosmatopoulos, E., & Tremori, A. (2021). M&S Based Testbed to Support V&V of Autonomous Resources Task Coordinator. In *Modelling and Simulation for Autonomous Systems: 7th International Conference, MESAS 2020, Prague, Czech Republic, October 21, 2020, Revised Selected Papers 7* (pp. 123-138). Springer International Publishing.
- (2) Karatzinis, G. D., **Apostolidis, S. D.**, Kapoutsis, A. C., Panagiotopoulou, L., Boutalis, Y. S., & Kosmatopoulos, E. B. (2020, September). Towards an integrated low-cost agricultural monitoring system with unmanned aircraft system. In *2020 International conference on unmanned aircraft systems (ICUAS)* (pp. 1131-1138). IEEE.
- (3) Orfanidis, G., **Apostolidis, S.**, Kapoutsis, A., Ioannidis, K., Kosmatopoulos, E., Vrochidis, S., & Kompatsiaris, I. (2019). Autonomous swarm of heterogeneous robots for surveillance operations. In *Computer Vision Systems: 12th International Conference, ICVS 2019*,

Thessaloniki, Greece, September 23-25, 2019, Proceedings 12 (pp. 787-796). Springer International Publishing.

c. Book Chapters

- (1) Orfanidis, G., **Apostolidis, S.**, Prountzos, G., Riga, M., Kapoutsis, A., Ioannidis, K., ... & Kompatsiaris, I. (2021). Border Surveillance Using Computer Vision-Enabled Robotic Swarms for Semantically Enriched Situational Awareness. In *Technology Development for Security Practitioners* (pp. 243-258). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

A

Spanning Tree Coverage - STC

One of the peculiarities of this method is that it uses two different grids, one for the representation of the ROI and the MST generation and one for the trajectory's generation. Specifically, the first grid has (square) cells with sides of length $2D$ (figure A.1(a)), where D corresponds to the distance that two sequential generated trajectories should have between them. From now on we will refer to these cells as mega-cells. This grid of mega-cells is used for the representation of the ROI. The nodes that will be used for the MST generation (figure A.1(b)) are placed in the center of the mega-cells and a standard methodology is applied (e.g., Prim [107], or Kruskal [108] algorithms) to construct the MST (figure A.1(c)). This MST is then used as a navigation guide for the coverage trajectory. For this reason, each mega-cell is split into four equal (square) sub-cells, with sides of length D . The centers of these sub-cells will be connected to create a line that circumnavigates the MST. This line corresponds to the output coverage trajectory that is used for the scanning of the whole region (figures A.1(d)-A.1(f)), and can be followed both clockwise or counter-clockwise.

One of the disadvantages of STC method is that while the sequential distance between trajectories is D , the discretization step for the representation of the ROI on the grid corresponds to $2D$ distance. This can create larger discretization error compared to other grid-based methods, something that can have a negative impact to the method's coverage performance in real-world applications. In addition to that, if no measures are taken during the generation of the MST, the output path may have an increased number of turns, something that is not desirable from a time and energy efficiency perspective. However, by controlling the costs for the connection among the nodes in the graph, before the generation of the MST, it is feasible to not only fix this issue, but achieve near-optimal results.

(a) Area representation on grid

(b) From cells to nodes

(c) MST generation

(d) MST as a navigation guide

(e) Circumnavigating path

(f) Final coverage trajectory

Figure A.1. Spanning Tree Coverage algorithm explained

B

End-to-End UAV Mission Planning Platform - Software Architecture

In order to provide an end-to-end solution able to deploy real-world UAV operations, along with the path planning methodologies presented and evaluated above, a custom software platform -including everything needed to perform real-life missions- has been developed. Figure B.1 presents the software architecture of the overall developed system, along with the technologies used.

Specifically, in the context of this work has been developed from scratch a web-based software application, including (i) a *user-friendly GUI*, (ii) the set of *novel multi-UAV path planning methodologies*, presented on the main body of the dissertation, and (iii) a *database* to store, manage and retrieve missions. In addition, a messaging mechanism and a custom-developed android application for the UAVs' controllers have been developed as well, in order to ensure the real-time communication with the UAVs.

As this appendix mostly describes work that required software development, and regards specific technologies, protocols, and APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), the platform description is performed from an end-user's point of

Figure B.1. Software platform architecture and technologies used

view, including only the absolutely necessary technical details.

B.1 Backend/Frontend Interaction

For the platform development has been employed a client-server architecture, a common paradigm for the web, meaning that the server delivers and manages most of the multi-UAV mission data and related computations that are going to be consumed by the client. In the client side (web browser), a modern and intuitive user interface powered by Material-UI framework and ReactJS (JavaScript library) has been implemented, that is supported by most browsers. In order to ensure real-time communication for the UAVs' positions and statuses between the client and the server, WebSockets protocol has been utilized, which is a popular technology used when servers need to push a lot of data, or frequently update the browser. In addition, the server exposes a RESTful (REpresentational State Transfer) API for computational requests and CRUD operations (Create, Read/retrieve, Update and Delete) for the database. The server side (backend) has been developed utilizing the Spring Framework for the Java Platform. Finally, the interaction between backend and the MySQL (Structured Query Language) database occurs with the Hibernate framework, an object-related mapping (ORM) library for the Java language.

B.2 User Interface - Interaction and Visualization

The GUI developed for the ground control station (GCS), is the main interaction layer of the platform with the user. Through it, the user is able to define, process, store, manage, execute, and supervise missions. In the right side of the GUI is placed a map, in order to locate and define the ROI, check the generated paths and supervise the progress of missions during the execution. Additionally, in the left side of GUI there is a toolbar, organized in three separate tabs. From the first tab of the toolbar, the user can access the database to retrieve stored missions or select to create new ones. As a next step, in the second tab the user can define the parameters for a new mission, or edit the ones of an already stored. The form fields and the available options of this tab, are different for each of the path planning approaches that are available in the platform, as in this step the user should define the specifications of a mission to be generated.

The final step to deploy a mission is included in the third tab, where the user can define the operational parameters (UAV taska and settings, camera, and gimbal settings), select the UAVs that should participate (stored in the database) and supervise the progress of the mission. Figure B.2 presents the

GUI visualization during the real-time execution of a coverage mission with 3 UAVs.

Figure B.2. Graphical User Interface during the mission execution supervision stage

B.3 Communication with UAVs - Android Application

In the controller of each UAV is connected a smartphone, running a mobile application that works as a user interface and interaction layer of the UAV with their operator. In the context of this work, a custom android application has been developed with the use of the DJI API (figure B.3), that takes the role of an intermediate communication layer of the overall platform with each UAV. This application is responsible to gather information (telemetry, photographs, statuses and mission logs) and transmit them to the backend of the platform. In addition, it visualizes mission's information and operational parameters, that could be useful for the operator.

The overall system has been setup with the objective to provide a high-level of autonomy for the missions. Based on this logic, the interaction of the platform's user with the whole system can be done entirely from the GCS, with no need to directly control the UAVs with the controllers or the smartphones' applications. However, at any time, based on the user's judgment, it is possible to take control and directly operate any of the UAVs, if needed.

Figure B.3. *Custom-developed android application*

Nomenclature

Nomenclature	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
BCM	Better Coverage Mode
CCM	Complete Coverage Mode
CETSP	Close Enough Traveling Salesman Problem
CPP	Coverage Path Planning
CRUD	Create, Read/retrieve, Update and Delete
d_c	Capturing Density
d_n	Nodes' Density
d_s	Scanning Density
FISR	Fast Inspection of Scattered Regions
FoV	Field of View
GCM	Geo-fenced Coverage Mode
GCS	Ground Control Station
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
GUI	Graphical User Interfphace
HFOV	Horizontal Field of View
mCPP	mutli-robot Coverage Path Planning

MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
MST	Minimum Spanning Tree
mTSP	multiple Traveling Salesman Problem
mTSPD	multiple Traveling Salesman Problem with Drones
mUDAI	multi-UAV Disjoint Areas' Inspection
NED	North East Down
NFZ	No-Fly-Zone
O	Obstacles
ORM	Object Related Mapping
p_f	Percentage of Frontlap
p_o	Percentage of Overlap
p_s	Percentage of Sidelap
POI	Point of Interest
POPCORN	Population Counting with Overhead Robotic Networks
res_h	Horizontal Resolution
res_v	Vertical Resolution
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
ROI	Region Of Interest
ROS	Robot Operating System
RS	Remote Sensing
s_x	Shifting - x axis
s_y	Shifting - y axis
SAR	Search and Rescue
SfM	Structure from Motion

SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theory
SoA	State-of-the-Art
SQL	Structured Query Language
STC	Spanning Tree Coverage
TSP	Traveling Salseman Problem
TSP-D	Traveling Salesman Problem with Drones
TSP-mD	Traveling Salseman Problem with multiple Drones
TW	Time-Window
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
v_n	Number of UAVs
VFOV	Vertical Field of View
VO	Visual Odometry
VRP	Vehicle Routing Problem
VTOL	Vertical Take-Off and Landing
WGS84	World Geodetic Coordinates 1984
X-STC	Extended Spanning Tree Coverage

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